

A New Ecosystem of Early Music Studies

MAKING CORPUS CREATION IN EARLY MUSIC REWARDING AND EFFECTIVE

*FINDING THE OPTIMUM BETWEEN
STANDARDISATION AND AUTONOMY*

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Abstract

Several early music projects, such as the Stanford Josquin Project, have demonstrated the potential for attaining valuable new musicological insights using a corpus-based approach. However, the available musical corpora tend to be relatively small and exhibit considerable variation in encoding practices. Aspiring corpus researchers are confronted with a lack of suitable data, which needs to be addressed before they can embark on their proper research.

The EarlyMuse Short Term Scientific Mission CORSICA has surveyed the current state of corpus creation and digital editing in early music. Based on this information, it has developed a vision for the future of corpus building in this field, which aims to speed up the production of digital encodings while respecting the autonomy of the encoders and acknowledging their efforts. This is important because much high-quality encoding is carried out outside the field of professional musicology, and engaging citizen scientists could help address the current shortage of research data.

The CORSICA team's vision is informed not only by a study of the available data, standards and technologies, but also by Human-Computer Interaction, placing human goals and values before the creation of technology and work processes. The core of the vision is that successful corpus creation must be an inclusive endeavour in terms of both technology and human participation. The report concludes with an implementation plan outlining the initial steps required to realise the vision.

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1 Introduction

This report presents a vision for the future of corpus creation and digital editing within the early music domain. It was developed in the EarlyMuse Short-Term Scientific Mission CORSICA (an acronym for *Creation Of eaRly muSic CorporA*).¹ In a nutshell, the problem addressed by this report is that there isn't enough data available for systematic computational analysis of early music. Since the number of potential participants in encoding projects is limited, we need to devise strategies that make data creation more effective, while at the same time the participants keep their sense of autonomy and feel respected for their contribution. Chapter 2 explains this problem further. The following chapters summarise the current state of early music corpus creation and digital editing from three perspectives: technology (Chapter 3), music research (Chapter 4) and community (Chapter 5). Chapter 6 organises the main insights from the state of the art by means of a PACT analysis, a framework for exploring a design situation from a human-centred perspective. Our human-centred approach is further elaborated in Chapter 7 by looking into the motivations, skills and work practices of professional and amateur corpus creators. This section also proposes a high-level model for collaborative projects. Based on the collected insights, the CORSICA team created a vision for the future of corpus creation (Chapter 8). As a starting point for the implementation of this vision, we present several recommendations to the EarlyMuse community as well as the wider community of researchers, practitioners and enthusiasts of early music (Chapter 9).

Throughout the report we highlight two areas in particular:

- various dimensions that describe the variety that can be observed in the early music encoding domain;
- human aspects of corpus creation such as uses, requirements, motivations, expertise and communities.

These relate to our view that diversity of approaches, motivations and technologies are an integral aspect of the music encoding domain and that it is more productive and rewarding to embrace these rather than strive for unification.

This report was written by the STSM participants and researchers from the Music Information Processing group of Utrecht University. Frans Wiering acted as the general editor of the document. Authors of the chapters and sections are named below the title. Unnamed text was written by Frans Wiering. The content of chapters 6 onwards represents the ideas and inputs of the entire group, not just the person who wrote the text.

¹ The proposal for this STSM is reproduced in Appendix 1. There is also a blog post about the STSM meeting in Utrecht in May 2024: <https://earlymuse.eu/publications/blog/creation-of-early-music-corpora-corsica-activities-and-a-workshop-about-building-collections-of-digital-editions/> (accessed 31 October 2025).

2 Problem description

In a nutshell, the main problem CORSICA addresses is: *we would like to conduct corpus research on early music but there aren't enough suitable encodings*. This description needs some unpacking, though. First, by early music we understand music composed before c. 1700 and secondly, we focus on polyphonic music. Despite the great variety of musics that fall within this description we believe that these share enough commonalities with respect to editing and encoding to separate them from monophonic and later music to be treated together.

The term 'corpus' is often used for large, bounded collections of texts or compositions, as in *Corpus mensuralis musicae*, a series of scholarly editions covering a large cross-section of late-medieval and Renaissance music.² A more precise description stems from linguistics:

corpora are balanced, often stratified collections of authentic, 'real world', text of speech or writing that aim to represent a given linguistic variety. Today, corpora are generally machine-readable data collections.³

Here we already encounter a first dimension in the encoding domain, between creation of digital editions on the one hand, and corpus creation for analytical purposes on the other. What connects the two is the availability of a machine-readable, manipulable encoding of the music that in the former scenario is rendered (usually) as a PDF, and in the latter is fed into analytical software such as music21.⁴

For corpus research the availability of encodings is obviously a crucial matter. Whereas textual corpora have been created at a large scale and are relatively homogeneous, musical corpora are comparatively small and display a considerable variety in encoding practices. They were often created during research projects with a specific focus, which then impacted encoding decisions. For pre-1700 polyphonic music, the situation is especially complicated: few corpora contain more than several hundreds of items; different types of music notation such as mensural notation and tablature pose specific encoding problems; and transcription to modern notation can be supported in multiple ways.

Some of the consequences of this situation are:

- available corpora are often not a representative selection from the known repertoire, making bias in the corpus almost inevitable (see Section 4.4);

² See <https://www.corpusmusicae.com/cmm.htm> (accessed 1 August 2025).

³ 'Corpus Linguistics,' Wikimedia Foundation, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Corpus_linguistics (accessed 23 October 2025). The definition from this article is based on C.F. Meyer, *English Corpus Linguistics: An Introduction*, 2nd ed. (Cambridge University Press, 2023), Section 1.1, 'Defining a Corpus.'

⁴ Music21 is 'a Python-based toolkit for computer-aided musicology', see <https://www.music21.org/music21docs/> (accessed 1 August 2025).

- quality and interoperability issues increase when using multiple corpora (see Section 3.3);
- choosing and mastering technologies involves a substantial intellectual challenge, at the expense of scarce research resources;
- off-the-beaten-track research requires an excessive amount of encoding effort, while studying that which has already been studied by others is easy;
- PhD students and early-career researchers do not have sufficient resources to embark on careers as digital musicologists.

On the other hand, there are some important positive developments:

- the emergence of MEI (Music Encoding Initiative⁵) as a versatile musicological encoding system with a growing user community (see Sections 3.1 and 4.1);
- improvements in Optical Music Recognition for early music (see Section 3.2);
- the general practice of musicologists to use music notation software to create their transcriptions;
- the widespread practice of online sharing of editions created by both professional and amateur musicians, and by citizen scientists possessing significant musicological expertise (see Sections 5.1 and 5.2);
- digital turn in musicology, accelerated by pandemic.⁶

The solution for the lack of encodings has often been sought in standardisation and training. These may indeed boost productivity, especially in the context of funded, large-scale projects such as Polish Musical Heritage.⁷ But elsewhere such endeavours have met with limited success for at least four interconnected reasons: complexity and limitations of tools; required time investment for learning; loss of already created work; and most importantly loss of autonomy. Since small-scale, autonomous projects are the norm for both music researchers and citizen scientists, it seems logical to take their autonomy, motivation and variety of practices as a starting point for designing a new ecology for early music corpus creation.⁸ This means first understanding why and how encoders (which to large extent means creators of digital editions) do their work. Next comes the question if, how, and under what conditions encoders would be willing to share their work, and how their contributions should be recognised. The last question is how their work could be effectively coordinated and supported with suitable tooling and processes. This document will present the first iteration in the elaboration of these ideas.

⁵ <https://music-encoding.org/> (accessed 1 August 2025).

⁶ F. Wiering and C. Inskip, 'The Impact of the Pandemic on Musicologists' Use of Technology,' *Digital Humanities Quarterly* 19, no. 2 (2025), <https://dhq.digitalhumanities.org/vol/19/2/000786/000786.html> (accessed 23 October 2025).

⁷ <https://polish.musicsources.pl/en> (accessed 1 August 2025).

⁸ It is standard practice in Human Computer Interaction to investigate human aspects of system design first and start designing processes and technology only after those are sufficiently understood. See e.g. D. Benyon, *Designing User Experience* (Pearson UK, 2019).

3 Corpora and technologies

The aim of this chapter is to give an overview of the current state of corpus creation from a primarily technological viewpoint: the availability of data and metadata, the software and the encoding formats used for data production. Section 3.1 presents an overview of the available early music encodings and their formats. There is considerable variation in technical approaches, making conversion between formats an issue. Section 3.2 describes Optical Music Recognition, a collection of technologies that potentially could reduce the need for tedious data entry work. Encodings are useless when we do not know what precisely they represent: metadata (Section 3.3) ideally records such information extensively, in a way that is shared between different resources. Section 3.4 describes how provenance information could be recorded by means of Data-Envelopes.

3.1 An overview of early music corpora and encoding systems

Music encoding and corpus building have been part of computational musicology since the 1960s and 1970s. The legendary Princeton Josquin Project aimed to encode the composer's complete output in IML (Intermediary Music Language).⁹ Numerous other projects produced larger or smaller collections using a variety of encoding systems.¹⁰ Unfortunately, through a near-perfect storm involving paradigm changes in both musicology and computing as well as personal circumstances and career choices of key researchers, only minimal traces of the encoding efforts from these early projects have survived. The main exception are the monophonic musical incipits of the RISM Catalog:¹¹ the work of encoding these in PAEC (Plaine and Easie Code) started in the 1960s and continues today.

The next stage in music encoding was shaped by the personal computer revolution and the emerging Internet. The MuseData and Humdrum corpora that go back to the 1980s are still available for research and KernScores (the current name of the main Humdrum corpus) is still growing. This is also when music enthusiasts started to create MIDI collections that later developed into resources like the Classical MIDI Files.

Today, encodings of early music can be found on numerous websites. Those that are known to the STSM participants are listed in Appendix 2, with a brief description of their content, estimated number of items, encoding system(s), urls, and some other

⁹ A. Mendel, 'Some Preliminary Attempts at Computer-Assisted Style Analysis in Music,' *Computers and the Humanities* 4, no. 2 (1969): 41-52, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/30199321>.

¹⁰ E. Selfridge-Field, ed., *Beyond MIDI: The Handbook of Musical Codes* (The MIT Press, 1998).

¹¹ See <https://rism.online/> and <https://opac.rism.info/> (accessed 24 October 2025).

name	description	documentation
ABC	Encoding system designed to notate music in plain text format, often used for encoding tunes but also for encoding complete scores	https://abcnotation.com/wiki/abc:standard
CMME	XML-based representation for mensural notation, supporting transcription to CMN	https://cmme.org/data/music/cmme.xsd (XML Schema)
Humdrum	Family of music representations in tabular format, such as **kern for CMN, **fret for tablatures and **mens for mensural notation	https://www.humdrum.org/rep/index.html ; https://doc.verovio.humdrum.org/humdrum/mens/ for **mens
IML	Encoding language for representing CMN on punch cards, developed for the Princeton Josquin Project	Robison (1967)
Lilypond	LaTeX-like typesetting language for music notation: early music notations and tablature are also supported	https://lilypond.org/doc/Documentation/notation/
MEI	XML-based representation for encoding music notation documents, customisable for a variety of notation types	https://music-encoding.org/guidelines/
MIDI	Binary format for storing music information as messages for an electronic instrument. Despite its limitations, it is also used for data exchange between music printing programs and as storage format	https://midi.org/midi-1-0-detailed-specification (version 1.0, 1996); https://midimusic.github.io/tech/midispec.html (version 1.1, 1999)
MuseData	Text-based encoding system for the logical content of scores in CMN	https://www.ccarh.org/publications/books/beyondmidi/online/musedata/
MusicXML	XML format for sharing sheet music between applications, with support for mensural notation and tablature	https://www.w3.org/2021/06/musicxml40/ (version 4.0, 2021)
PAEC	System for representing music notation with typewriter symbols, mostly used for encoding incipits	https://www.iaml.info/plaine-easie-code
Tab	Encoding system for typesetting lute music	https://www.cs.dartmouth.edu/~wbc/lute/AboutTab.html
Tabcode	ASCII format for French and Italian lute tablature	https://igor.gold.ac.uk/isms/ecolm/?page=TabCode

Table 1: Music encoding formats mentioned in this report.

information. A comprehensive overview of music corpora research is lacking and very likely some useful collections of early music encodings have escaped our notice. Most scholarly corpora, such as the Stanford-based Josquin Research Project (JRP), the Electronic Medieval Music Score Archive Project (EMMSAP) and Electronic Linked Annotated Unified Tablature Edition (E-LAUTE) have a rather specific focus and contain less than a hundred to a few thousand encodings. The largest corpora stem from individual or collective projects by citizen scientists who edit vocal and lute music. Helping the community by sharing music editions seems to be an important motivation for contributing. Reusable encodings are generally a by-product of their effort and may not be made available to others. There is a wide range of editorial approaches, and the quality of the work is rather uneven. Nevertheless, the best and most active contributors to Choral Public Domain Library (CPDL) and similar online collections have produced substantial numbers of editions and encodings that offer an interesting potential for musicological research. For the scholarly perspective on several of these corpora see Section 4.1).

Numerous encoding formats are employed in the corpora (see Table 1 for a survey). MuseScore, one of the most popular software tools for music editing, supports the open encoding format MusicXML. Other formats are regularly used as well, especially in music research, such as MEI (Music Encoding Initiative; with extensive support for critical editions and active development of markup for non-standard notation forms), Humdrum, Lilypond, CMME (Computerized Mensural Music Editing; for mensural notation) and various systems for encoding lute tablature. Many projects support MIDI as a format for playback and data exchange. As a storage format it has significant shortcomings, for example the inability to encode lyrics.

The basic task of entering music into the computer can be time-consuming, error-prone and (depending on one's motivation) tedious, even when encoding only a limited set of properties. Good tooling (Graphical User Interface design in particular) can obviously make a difference. Optical Music Recognition (OMR) may offer a solution in some cases (see Section 3.2 for an in-depth discussion), but even the best OMR output currently needs substantial error correction and post-processing.

Different communities of encoders can be identified, each with its own mix of aims, tools, encoding format and publication practices (e.g. MEI, CPDL, Lilypond, Tab). While it is unlikely (for both intellectual and social reasons) that these communities will eventually merge, it makes sense to study how and to what extent one community's output can be another community's input. Many resources offer encodings in multiple formats that are automatically derived from the storage format. Tools for conversion of encodings include:

- LuteConv,¹² a command-line tool for conversion between lute tablature encoding formats, also available as a Web interface and API for ease of use;¹³

¹² <https://bitbucket.org/bayleaf/luteconv/> (accessed 24 October 2025).

¹³ <https://luteconv.mdw.ac.at/> (accessed 24 October 2025).

- Verovio for conversion of MusicXML and CMME into MEI;¹⁴
- Verovio Humdrum for conversion of Humdrum into MEI and MusicXML.¹⁵

Since each encoding system has a particular focus (and often its own design philosophy) conversion between encoding systems is often not straightforward: information may be lost, its meaning may be subtly altered, or inference of missing information may be necessary.¹⁶

3.2 Optical Music Recognition: hopes and realities

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Taking as point of departure the heterogeneity of existent early music manuscripts, prints, modern printed editions, and digital encodings of various kinds, a natural starting question would be how to homogenize these sources to form a corpus of consistently encoded scores to be used in dynamic editions. As the task of manually transcribing scores is both tedious and time-consuming, scholars have started looking at Optical Music Recognition (OMR) to significantly shorten and streamline this process. For the purpose of the present STSM, viewing the transcription and encoding process as a continuum where, at one end, there is the fully manual labour, and at the other, the fully automatized workflow, we can ask where on this line current technology exists, and where it is indeed desirable to be.

In a survey of the research field, Calvo-Zaragoza et al. define OMR as ‘how to computationally read music notation in documents’.¹⁷ Unpacking this, the meaning of ‘computationally reading’ something is explained as the recovery of not only the music notation symbols, but also the musical semantics (the information of what should be played when). The ‘documents’, in turn, consist of digital images of the source material, and can vary significantly in both quality and quantity. An important challenge lies then in how to train OMR models to recognize and retrieve the relevant information. In order to chart the decisions and processes involved, the authors provide a taxonomy of OMR, consisting of 3 stages: inputs, system architectures and outputs. We follow this taxonomy in the discussion below.

¹⁴ <https://www.verovio.org/> (accessed 24 October 2025); D. Fiala et al., ‘A New XML Conversion Process for Mensural Music Encoding: CMME_to_MEI (via Verovio),’ paper presented at the Music Encoding Conference, London, 4 June 2025. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2507.15991>.

¹⁵ <https://verovio.humdrum.org/> (accessed 24 October 2025).

¹⁶ L. Pugin, ‘Interaction with Music Encoding,’ in *“Ei, dem alten Herrn zoll’ ich Achtung gern” Festschrift für Joachim Veit zum 60. Geburtstag*, ed. K. Richts and P. Stadler (Allitera Verlag, 2016): 617–630, <https://musicconn.qucosa.de/api/qucosa%3A23351/attachment/ATT-0/> (accessed 24 October 2025); Fiala et al., ‘A New XML Conversion Process.’

¹⁷ J. Calvo-Zaragoza et al. 2020, ‘Understanding Optical Music Recognition,’ *ACM Computing Surveys* 53, no. 4 (2020), article 77, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3397499>.

Considering inputs, what is considered relevant information may vary according to the researcher. Any OMR application would have to be designed around the specific conditions relevant to the research aims of its users. Calvo-Zaragoza et al. provide a useful overview of common input conditions, reproduced in Figure 1.

Figure 1. OMR input taxonomy (reproduced after Calvo-Zaragoza et al. 2020).

The input signal can be offline (an image) or online (notation being written, e.g. on a tablet). Production modes are typesetting and handwriting (sometimes found in the same source). OMR may have to deal with a variety of notation forms, ranging from Common Western notation to historical, non-western and experimental notations. In addition to monophony, notational complexity distinguishes homophonic (a single line of chords), polyphonic (multiple monophonic voices on a single staff), and pianoform complexity (cannot be decomposed in single monophonic voices). Document quality refers to the source itself, while image acquisition refers to the production process, which in the case of early music may range from high-quality digital facsimiles to for example digitised old microfilms.

It becomes clear from this diagram that OMR of early music sources has a particular complexity that is quite different from the more common scenario of processing more complex but generally decent-quality CMN: handwritten, degraded sources using non-CMN notation that may be distorted in digitisation are not an uncommon phenomenon.

There are various systems which deal with the information retrieval process in different ways. These can be divided into *modular*, *end-to-end*, and *interactive* systems. A modular system pipeline usually consists of preprocessing, object detection, notation assembly, and finally encoding. An end-to-end system tries to accomplish these stages in a single process, often by means of a deep learning model. Although end-to-end systems are common in the neighbouring field of optical text recognition (OCR), the challenges of music semantics have made the same progress in OMR difficult. These issues are nevertheless being tackled.¹⁸ The

¹⁸ J. Mayer et al., 'Practical End-to-End Optical Music Recognition for Pianoform Music,' in *Document Analysis and Recognition - ICDAR 2024*, eds. E.H. Barney Smith et al., Lecture Notes in Computer Science, 14809 (Springer, 2024), https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-70552-6_4; R. He and J. Yao, 'End-to-End Optical Music Recognition with Attention Mechanism and Memory Units Optimization,' in *Pattern Recognition and Computer Vision*,

perhaps most realistic alternative for an OMR application with a wide purpose, however, may be an interactive system which lets the user be a part of the OMR process. Acknowledging that an encoding is always a translation, or reduction of the source in some way (see below, Section 4.2), and that there will always be irregularities in the sources demanding human interpretation, an efficient interactive system can be said to be the optimal tool for speeding up the encoding process. An interactive OMR tool lets the user view the recognized symbols superimposed on top of the original source image for easy inspection and correction (Aruspix,¹⁹ Audiveris²⁰ and MuRET²¹ are examples of such systems, the first using ASCII, the second MusicXML and the last MEI as its primary output format). On the continuum between completely manual and completely automated information retrieval, then, a fully automated process may not be the most desirable.

Regarding outputs, Calvo-Zaragoza et al. propose four aims: document metadata extraction, search, replayability, structured encoding. While the last is the most relevant for our purposes, a significant part of OMR research for historical sources goes into search-oriented OMR applications. The underlying thought is that, while OMR technology is still far from perfect, aligning OMR output with digital facsimiles combined with error-tolerant, fuzzy search mechanisms may in practice provide powerful search mechanisms that significantly enhance the access to musical content. An early example is the searchable online facsimile of the *Liber usualis*.²² A similar initiative is the OmniOMR project,²³ aiming 'to provide full-text search functionality in musical documents in diverse library collections', using technology developed in the context of MuRET. Using the same technology, the Bavarian State Library is currently creating a search environment for 16th and 17th-century printed

eds. Q. Liu et al., Lecture Notes in Computer Science, 14426 (Springer, 2024)

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-8432-9_32; A. Ríos-Vila et al., 'Sheet Music Transformer: End-To-End Optical Music Recognition beyond Monophonic Transcription,' in *Document Analysis and Recognition - ICDAR 2024*, eds. E.H. Barney Smith et al., Lecture Notes in Computer Science, 14809 (Springer, 2024) https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-70552-6_2.

¹⁹ <https://www.aruspix.net/> (accessed 25 October 2025).

²⁰ <https://github.com/Audiveris> (accessed 24 October 2025).

²¹ J.M. Iñesta et al., 'MuRET as a Software for the Transcription of Historical Archives,' in *Proceedings of the 2nd Workshop on Reading Music Systems*, eds. J. Calvo-Zaragoza and A. Pacha (2019): 12-15, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2212.00380>.

²² A. Hankinson et al., 'Digital Document Image Retrieval Using Optical Music Recognition,' in *Proceedings of the 13th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference*, eds. F. Gouyon et al. (2012): 577-582, https://ismir2012.ismir.net/event/papers/577_ISMIR_2012.pdf (accessed 25 October 2025).

²³ J. Hajič jr. et al., 'The OmniOMR Project,' in *Proceedings of the 5th Workshop on Reading Music Systems*, eds. J. Calvo-Zaragoza et al. (2023): 12-14, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2311.04091>.

sources and manuscript choirbooks.²⁴ Using a different technology, Aruspix,²⁵ the F-TEMPO project provides similar access to printed early music from multiple European libraries.²⁶ Designed specifically for transcribing typeset mensural notation for edition, Aruspix stands out as an OMR application with unusually good performance on high-quality scans.²⁷ But even the highest precision and recall rates reported (95-97%) shows that for the creating of encodings that meet musicological transcription standards human intervention remains essential.

While well-known OMR projects such as SIMSSA²⁸ continue to be developed, the research field is also rich in new approaches. Those that have musicological users in mind are often reported at venues such as WORMS²⁹ and DLfM.³⁰ Some of these concentrate on the challenges to machine learning when the data is scarce.³¹ Others offer new interactive tools, like OMRAT,³² or focus on improving some stage in the

²⁴ J. Umbreit and S. Schumann, 'OMR on Early Music Sources at the Bavarian State Library with MuRET - Prototyping, Automating, Scaling,' in *Proceedings of the 6th Workshop on Reading Music Systems*, eds. J. Calvo-Zaragoza et al. (2024): 43-45, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2411.15741>.

²⁵ <https://www.aruspix.net/> (accessed 24 October 2025).

²⁶ T. Crawford et al., 'Exploring Early Vocal Music and Its Lute Arrangements: Using F-TEMPO as a Musicological Tool,' in *DLfM '23: Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Digital Libraries for Musicology*, ed. M.E. Thomae (Association for Computing Machinery, 2023): 77-81, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3625135.3625142>.

²⁷ L. Pugin and T. Crawford, 'Evaluating OMR on the Early Music Online Collection,' in *Proceedings of the 14th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference*, eds. A. de Souza Britto jr. et al. (2013): 439-444, <https://archives.ismir.net/ismir2013/paper/000065.pdf> (accessed 25 October 2025).

²⁸ I. Fujinaga and G. Vigiensoni, 'Optical Music Recognition Workflow for Medieval Music Manuscripts,' in *Proceedings of the 5th Workshop on Reading Music Systems*, eds. J. Calvo-Zaragoza et al. (2023): 4-6, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2311.04091>

²⁹ <https://sites.google.com/view/worms2024> (accessed 24 October 2025; there is no umbrella WORMS url)

³⁰ <https://dlfm.web.ox.ac.uk/home> (accessed 24 October 2025).

³¹ C. Penarrubia et al., 'Contrastive Self-Supervised Learning for Optical Music Recognition,' in *Document Analysis Systems. DAS 2024*, eds. G. Sfikas and G. Retsinas, Lecture Notes in Computer Science, 14994 (Springer, 2024), https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-70442-0_19; A. Roselló et al., 'Source-Free Domain Adaptation for Optical Music Recognition,' in *Document Analysis and Recognition - ICDAR 2024*, eds. E.H. Barney Smith et al., Lecture Notes in Computer Science, 14809 (Springer, 2024), https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-70552-6_2.

³² S. Graczyk et al., 'An Online Tool for Semi-Automatically Annotating Music Scores for Optical Music Recognition,' in *Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Digital Libraries for Musicology*, ed. D.M. Weigl (Association for Computing Machinery, 2024), 73-77, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3660570.3660571>.

music recognition process.³³ Important contributions has also been made to the discussion of the potential of AI and neural networks in early music studies.³⁴ In designing future corpora of encoded music, then, these are important aspects to consider.

3.3 Metadata and interoperability

Peter van Kranenburg and Frans Wiering

Encodings and digital editions need to be adequately described to be usable for research. In practice, however, the amount metadata provided with the items is variable and often limited. Specifying just title and composer name for a composition, as some resources do, may be insufficient for precise identification even for works in the classical canon. In early music there are several factors that necessitate richer metadata. The 'text' of a composition is generally not a given but must be constructed from its sources. Compositions often exist in multiple versions, targeted at different performance resources or occasions, with no clear difference in authority. Notation is transformed during the editorial process, whether by transcription, transposition, correction, interpretation, supplying missing information, or other actions. These three factors make it difficult in early music to speak of *the* score of a composition, let alone *the* encoding of it. Therefore, information that documents provenance and processing of the music notation is indispensable and should be recorded in its metadata.

Support for metadata varies between encoding systems. For example, MusicXML provides `<work>` and `<identification>` elements with their child elements. For `<work>` these are the optional `<work-number>`, `<work-title>` and `<opus>` elements. `<identification>` may include `<creator>` and `<source>` elements, as well as `<encoding>` for information about the creation of the encoding.³⁵ Humdrum allows for an extended range of metadata including composer, work, source, publication, copyright and edition information to be included in the file.³⁶ MEI offers an even richer, more structured tagset for metadata. It is based on the TEI header³⁷ format but also implements the FRBR (Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records)

³³ L. Tuggener et al., 'Real World Music Object Recognition,' *Transactions of the International Society for Music Information Retrieval* 7, no. 1 (2024): 1-14, <https://doi.org/10.5334/tismir.157>.

³⁴ See for example X. Fresquet, 'Artificial Neural Networks and Medieval Music,' *Early Music* 52, no. 3 (2024): 298-317, <https://doi.org/10.1093/em/caae039>.

³⁵ <https://www.w3.org/2021/06/musicxml40/musicxml-reference/elements/> (accessed 12 August 2025).

³⁶ <https://www.humdrum.org/reference-records/> (accessed 12 August 2025).

³⁷ MEI header documentation: <https://music-encoding.org/guidelines/v5/content/metadata.html> (accessed 25 October 2025); TEI header documentation: <https://tei-c.org/release/doc/tei-p5-doc/en/html/HD.html> (accessed 25 October 2025).

model.³⁸ This is particularly interesting since FRBR allows the coordination of works and source instances as well as different variants of a composition (for this, the FRBR category 'expression' is used). It is doubtful that the different metadata formats are compatible at all, not just because of differences in structure but also because the format of the metadata fields is generally free and specific guidelines for their use are generally missing.

Truly rich and controlled metadata can be found in various source catalogues, RISM³⁹ and DIAMM⁴⁰ in particular. Some of these resources are coordinated, for example by using common identifiers for sources and items they contain. But such unification is only partial: some resources use the Census Catalogue⁴¹ library sigla (for example *UtreR* for the Utrecht University Library), others those developed for RISM (*N1-UU* for the same library). For personal names, place names and works VIAF (Virtual International Authority File) identifiers can be used.⁴² An open challenge is how items in sources can be linked to compositions (or expressions of compositions) efficiently, without having to resort to manual work.⁴³ If, however, such linking involving multiple resources is available at sufficient scale, the potential of Linked Open Data comes into view.

Within the ERC funded Polifonia Project (2021-2024), a comprehensive music ontology has been designed, the Polifonia Ontology Network.⁴⁴ The MusicMeta module is of particular interest in the context of the current report. It offers a semantic model for representation of metadata for music entities. This module has been designed to be interoperable with existing ontologies while adding an abstraction layer. The MusicMeta ontology module has been aligned with FRBR, DOREMUS,⁴⁵ and Wikidata,⁴⁶ allowing data integration from various existing databases.

³⁸ K. Richts, 'Die FRBR Customization im Datenformat der Music Encoding Initiative (MEI).' (master's thesis, Cologne University of Applied Sciences, 2013), <https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:hbz:79pbc-2013103042>.

³⁹ Répertoire International des Sources Musicales, <https://rism.info/> (accessed 31 October 2025).

⁴⁰ Digital Image Archive of Medieval Music, <https://www.diamm.ac.uk/> (accessed 31 October 2025).

⁴¹ J. Call et al., *Census-Catalogue of Manuscript Sources of Polyphonic Music, 1400-1550* (American Institute of Musicology, Hänssler-Verlag, 1979-1988), 5 vols.

⁴² <https://viaf.org/> (accesses 25 October 2025).

⁴³ RISM devoted an entire conference to the linking of items and compositions in 2019, see <https://rism.info/de/publications/conferences/work-level-2019.html> (accessed 25 October 2025).

⁴⁴ <https://polifonia-project.github.io/ecosystem/polifonia-project/ontology-network/header.html> (accessed 29 January 2026)

⁴⁵ Doing Reusable MUSical data, <https://www.doremus.org/> (accessed 2 February 2026)

⁴⁶ <https://www.wikidata.org/> (accessed 31 October 2025).

In general, the field would benefit from an integrated network of data sources that could answer questions such as ‘Given a composer name, what are their known compositions?’, or ‘Given a composition, in what sources does it appear’. During the STSM, we performed a case study to get an impression of the level of integration and completeness of various metadata sources concerning these questions. We chose a composition of one of the most prominent Renaissance composers, Orlando de Lassus: the chanson *Je l’ayme bien*.

The particular source we are interested in is the *Codex Lerma*⁴⁷ (c. 1590), which we studied during the STSM. *Je l’ayme bien* is included at folios 8v and 9r. Because this source is a relatively unimportant one for the transmission of compositions by Lassus, and this composition is not one of his more famous works, we assume that the results of our case study are indicative for the situation concerning metadata about Renaissance music.

We queried a number of data sources to find other sources and editions for this composition. The results can be summarized as follows.

- Répertoire International des Sources Musicales (RISM)
 - The composition is in the RISM, but not this particular source (*Codex Lerma*)
- Digital Image Archive of Medieval Music (DIAMM)
 - The *Codex Lerma* is in the DIAMM database
 - The list of works in *Codex Lerma* is incomplete
 - There is a dead link to the scan at Utrecht University Library
- Wikidata
 - The composer is present
 - The composition is not present
- Muziekweb⁴⁸
 - The composer is present
 - Three instances of a recording are present
- MusicBrainz⁴⁹
 - The composer is present
 - The list of works by Lassus is incomplete
- Choral Public Domain Library (CPDL)⁵⁰
 - Five editions of this composition are present
 - Only one includes a reference to a source

⁴⁷ Universiteitsbibliotheek, Utrecht, Netherlands, Hs. 3 L 16, see <https://www.uu.nl/en/special-collections/collections/manuscripts/modern-manuscripts/codex-lerma> (accessed 31 October 2025).

⁴⁸ <https://www.muziekweb.nl/> (accessed 31 October 2025).

⁴⁹ <https://musicbrainz.org/> (accessed 31 October 2025).

⁵⁰ <https://www.cpdlib.org/> (accessed 31 October 2025).

- International Music Score Library Project (IMSLP) / Petrucci Music Library⁵¹
 - The composer is present
 - The list of works is incomplete
 - There are 3 editions and 4 arrangements of this composition.
 - There is a dead link to CPDL caused by a spelling variation ('amerai' instead of 'aimerai').

During this exercise, one particular disappointment was that there does not seem to exist a machine-readable data source that gives all compositions for such a prominent composer as Lassus, although there exists a *Lasso Verzeichnis* (LV) in which our composition is number 39 (as reported in IMSLP).⁵²

These results show that even for a prominent composer such as Lassus it is not possible to automatically retrieve the requested overviews from the various data sources, despite the promises of Linked Open Data. The level of integration at machine-readable level is disappointing.

3.4 Provenance

Marnix van Berchum

Provenance information provides the 'history' of the content one is using at the moment, tracing all intermediate steps of its state. Basically, it models the changes of the state of the content, answering the questions on the agents involved in the changes: *Who?, How?, What?, When?, Why?, and Where?*. Provenance information gives the context for (re)use and enables the reproduction of research results. Two types of provenance can be distinguished: provenance of the content and technical provenance. Figure 2 shows, as example, a simplified view of where provenance information 'lives' in the context of early music editions. At the level of a corpus provenance information should include information on how the corpus came into being and which selections were made by whom (for more activities which can be captured as provenance, see Section 6.3).

Figure 2. Sources of provenance information.

⁵¹ <https://imslp.org/> (accessed 31 October 2025).

⁵² H. Leuchtman, *Orlando di Lasso. Seine Werke in zeitgenössischen Drucken 1555-1687* (Bärenreiter, 2001), 3 vols.

Three stages of the edition are discerned: the Source, a Transcription, and the (final) Edition. At each stage relevant elements should be captured and documented:

1. **Source:** Which source or sources is/are used (siglum, description, identifier, etc.)? Is the physical item or a (digital) reproduction used? If a reproduction: how is the source reproduced, with what technology, settings, etc.? Information on the source may extend to detailed analysis of the codicological and paleographical status of a source.
2. **Transcription:** What is the format of the transcription (paper, MEI, **kern, etc.)? Who made the transcription, etc. (i.e. metadata of the transcription)?
3. **Edition:** What is the format of the transcription (paper, MEI, **kern, etc.)? Who made the edition, etc. (i.e. metadata of the edition)?

Other provenance information maps the (technical) processes, when moving from one stage to the other. It includes answers to the *Who?, How?, What?, When?, Why?, and Where?* questions:

1. How is the transcription made: manually or (semi)automatically with OMR? Which software is used, with which version? Which choices are made in the transcription (e.g. note values, error correction, etc.)? Why and on what basis are transcription conventions used?
2. What conversions are made between the transcription and the edition (e.g. from MEI to PDF)? Which software is used, with which version? Are more editorial choices made, and if so, by whom, on what basis etc.?

Examples of implementation of provenance information, at the larger scale of a corpus, can be found at the Huygens Institute for History and Culture of the Netherlands.⁵³ In case of provenance of content, addressing ‘the particular needs and challenges of the cultural heritage field’ with regard to the heterogeneous nature (complex, diverse, uncertain, incomplete etc.) of humanities data, the data management department of this research institute developed the so-called ‘Data-Envelopes’.⁵⁴ This ‘documentation framework’ captures all intricacies of the data ‘while combining machine-readability and user-friendliness’. Furthermore, the data-envelopes take into account the legal and ethical sensitivities of the data. The combination of information is aimed at the potential (re)use of the data, by both human and machine agents. It is ‘structured into modular sections, each designed to encapsulate different facets of the dataset in a systematic manner’, see Figure 3.

⁵³ <https://www.huygens.knaw.nl/en/> (accessed 25 October 2025).

⁵⁴ See the summarising article on this work: M. Luthra and M. Eskevich, ‘Data-Envelopes for Cultural Heritage: Going beyond Datasheets,’ in *Proceedings of the Workshop on Legal and Ethical Issues in Human Language Technologies @ LREC-COLING 2024*, eds. I. Siegert and K. Choukri (ELRA and ICCL, 2024): 52-65, <https://aclanthology.org/2024.legal-1.9> (accessed 25 October 2025). All following quotes taken from this article.

Figure 3. Modules available in the Huygens Data-Envelopes, taken from Luthra and Eskevich.⁵⁵

Figure 4. Flow diagram of provenance trails generated in the REPUBLIC project.

⁵⁵ M. Luthra and M. Eskevich, 'Data-Envelopes for Cultural Heritage.'

For the capture of technical provenance information an implementation was devised in the REPUBLIC project.⁵⁶ The goal of the project was to ‘digitally unlock all resolutions (decisions) that the States General [of the Netherlands] took during their existence as an autonomous political entity (1576–1796).’ These resolutions can be found in a scanned version of the originals in the National Archives and are made available in an online search interface (relating to the scope of this paper, it can be considered as a fully searchable digital corpus of resolutions).⁵⁷ All data processing steps were tracked, making ‘it possible to trace down to the smallest detail the decisions we have made in the entire process from scanning the resolution books to displaying them in the web interface’.⁵⁸ Figures 4 and 5 show a schematic (‘flow’) and detailed view (‘data trail’) of the provenance trails generated in the project. In the latter view the different questions (*Who?*, *How?*, *What?* etc.) can be clearly seen, including links to external resources, for the individual involved (ORCID) and the script used.

Figure 5. Detailed view of a provenance trail generated in the REPUBLIC project. Developed by Team Structured Data / Digital Infrastructure department of the KNAW Humanities Cluster, <https://di.huc.knaw.nl/home-en.html>.

⁵⁶ See <https://goetgevonden.nl/> (accessed 25 October 2025).

⁵⁷ The online interface is available at <https://app.goetgevonden.nl> (accessed 25 October 2025).

⁵⁸ See <https://goetgevonden.nl/en/the-method/provenance/> (accessed 25 October 2025). The software developed by the shared Digital Infrastructure department / Team Structured Data is available at <https://github.com/knaw-huc/provenance> (accessed 25 October 2025).

4 Looking at corpora from a scholarly viewpoint

This chapter describes the dealings of scholars with corpora. Section 4.1 on systematic corpus creation resumes the treatment of corpora from Section 3.1 through an in-depth discussion of some important scholarly corpora of early music from the perspective of the researcher who wishes to use them. Section 4.2 continues this perspective with an analysis of analytical tasks and the challenges that an analyst might face in the execution of those tasks. A different but related perspective emerges in Section 4.3, namely that of critical editing in the digital age. Finally, Section 4.4 presents the perspective of the researcher who, in the absence of a complete encoding of everything, still wants to assemble a representative selection of composition for their research.

4.1 Systematic corpora creation: where do we come from and where are we now?

Esperanza Rodríguez-García

The impulse to assemble comprehensive music corpora is deeply embedded in musicology. From its institutional beginnings, the field has prioritised the creation of cohesive collections of music. Notably, the emergence of musicology as a scientific discipline in the mid-nineteenth century was closely linked to the publication of monumental editions, such as the *Bach-Gesellschaft Ausgabe* (from 1851), the *Händel-Gesellschaft Edition* (from 1858), and the *Opera omnia Ioannis Petraloysii Praenestini* (from 1862), among the earliest of their kind. Over a century later, the rise of computational musicology has echoed this same impetus, especially as ‘big data’ methods gained traction in the 2000s.⁵⁹ This trend has only accelerated with the popularisation of digital editing tools, online open repositories, and increasingly sophisticated analytical technologies. Collaborative efforts between historical musicologists and information technologists have resulted in more accessible digital tools, fostering broader scholarly engagement with digital corpora.

My direct experience with such corpora stems from my ‘Coordinator of Sacred Repertories’ role at the *Archive of Iberian Polyphony*.⁶⁰ This small and still-incomplete repository, which contains 130 works of Iberian origin, was developed as part of the project *The Anatomy of Late 15th- and Early 16th-Century Iberian Polyphonic Music* (2016–2019), directed by João Pedro d’Alvarenga at Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Portugal. The *Archive* offers critical editions in PDF format accompanied by extensive metadata, though it does not currently include encoded music.

⁵⁹ S. Tuppen et al., ‘Library Catalogue Records as a Research Resource: Introducing “a Big Data History of Music,”’ *Fontes Artis Musicae* 63 (2016): 67–88, <https://doi.org/10.1353/fam.2016.0011>.

⁶⁰ <https://iberianpolyphony.fcsh.unl.pt/> (accessed 25 October 2025).

Nonetheless, it provided the foundation for a dataset of Iberian and Franco-Flemish motets ca. 1500, created to explore stylistic traits within these repertoires and to investigate the authorship of two anonymous motets. In collaboration with Cory McKay (Marianopolis College), we analysed this dataset using *jSymbolic* for feature-based comparisons.⁶¹ The resulting corpus consists of 175 motets encoded as MIDI files.⁶² These were compiled by reusing edited materials from the *Archive* and supplementing them with works drawn from other repositories. The Iberian motets were modelled on editions produced by the *Archive*. The Franco-Flemish items were adapted from the *Josquin Research Project*. Newly produced scores were explicitly created to fill gaps in the repertoire. Given the heterogeneous nature of the sources, we followed a workflow aligned with the methodologies and standards outlined by Julie Cumming, Cory McKay, et al. in their seminal 2018 article, which systematises best practices for building interoperable symbolic corpora of pre-1600 Western music.⁶³ Along the encoding process, the crucial principle was to keep consistency. Whatever their origin, all the items were encoded as MusicXML files using Sibelius. They were manually adjusted and revised to create the master files and then exported as MIDI. Finally, they were double-checked with *jSymbolic* to detect any possible inconsistency.

As a historical musicologist focusing on analysis, my assessment will concentrate on scholarly corpora that provide encoded outputs suitable for computational analysis. I will highlight the most notable examples without attempting to be exhaustive but rather aiming to underscore trends and challenges in the field.

The earliest scholarly initiatives appeared in the first decade of the 21st century. Similar to the formation of traditional corpora of critical editions, they were discrete, uncoordinated and responded to various objectives.

One such effort was the *Tomas Luis de Victoria database*, a personal project by Nancho Álvarez, mainly intended for performance.⁶⁴ While it does not qualify as a scholarly repository, it merits mention here as a representative case that illustrates the limitations of non-academic corpora for scholarly purposes.

Started around 2002 and significantly updated in 2009, the project initially focused on the works of Tomás Luis de Victoria, eventually expanding to include

⁶¹ E. Rodríguez-García and C. McKay, 'Composer Attribution of Renaissance Motets: A Case Study Using Statistical Features and Machine Learning,' in *The Anatomy of Iberian Polyphony around 1500*, eds. E. Rodríguez-García and J. P. d'Alvarenga (Reichenberger 2021): 401–38.

⁶² E. Rodríguez-García, & C. McKay, 'Composer Attribution of Renaissance Motets (Iberian Polyphony around 1500): MIDI and Extracted Features,' dataset, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4027957>.

⁶³ J. Cumming et al., 'Methodologies for Creating Symbolic Corpora of Western Music Before 1600,' in *Proceedings of the 19th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference*, eds. E. Gómez et al. (2018): 348–354, <https://archives.ismir.net/ismir2018/paper/000026.pdf> (accessed 26 October 2025).

⁶⁴ <https://victoria.uma.es/> (accessed 26 October 2025).

compositions by Morales, Guerrero, Vásquez, and other Spanish Renaissance composers. An impressive undertaking, it currently offers over 1,500 encoded works. However, the editions are not critical, and the encodings lack standardised metadata essential for robust scholarly analysis. Furthermore, its reliance on Lilypond and MIDI encoding formats presents challenges for interoperability and reusability. Another early example is the *Computerised Mensural Music Editing Project* (CMME), created in 2006 by Theodor Dumitrescu and Marnix van Berchum.⁶⁵ Although it only contained 59 encoded pieces,⁶⁶ the project was groundbreaking in its approach to handling the complexities of mensural notation. However, its tailored encoding format (.cmme) limits compatibility with other formats.⁶⁷

The disjointed landscape of digital music notation in the early 2000s – described by Hankinson et al. (2011) as ‘highly fragmented’ – began to be more systematically addressed in 2010.⁶⁸ The *Josquin Research Project*, launched in 2010 and led by Jessie Rodin and Craig Sapp, represents a turning point in standardising procedures.⁶⁹ Designed with interoperability and reusability criteria in mind, it houses 902 works by Josquin and his contemporaries, offering a broad range of formats. In addition to the standard encoding trio of MusicXML, MEI and MIDI, the database includes Humdrum, MuseData, NoteArray, and JSON Piano Roll. It also features MP3 and PDF formats with/without editorial accidentals alongside an embedded analytical tool. It has helped establish a widely accepted model for what academically oriented music corpora should provide.

Similarly, *Tasso in Music*, directed by Emiliano Ricciardi and Craig Sapp, launched in 2015 (and still ongoing), contains a collection of 778 music settings of Tasso’s poetry.⁷⁰ The project also offers a variety of encoding formats and capabilities. Another lesser-known dataset, the *Symbolically Encoded Il Lauro Secco* (SEILS) directed by Emilia Parada-Cabaleiro, is worth mentioning.⁷¹ It comprises 30 pieces in both early and modern notation, amounting to 150 codified scores. Its range of formats is even more expansive, catering to both analysis and OMR applications: LilyPond, MusicXML, MIDI, Finale, **kern, **mens, MEI, agnostic, semantic, and PDF formats in both white mensural and modern notation. However, its hosting on GitHub – while an accessible platform – makes it somewhat more challenging to discover than a standard webpage, hindering findability.

⁶⁵ <http://www.cmme.org/> (accessed 26 October 2025).

⁶⁶ And around 200 pieces in the Github Repository <https://github.com/tdumitrescu/cmme-music> (accessed 26 October 2025).

⁶⁷ But see Fiala et al., ‘A New XML Conversion Process.’

⁶⁸ A. Hankinson et al., ‘The Music Encoding Initiative as a Document-Encoding Framework,’ in *Proceedings of the 12th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference*, eds. A. Klapuri and C. Leider (2011): 293–298, <https://archives.ismir.net/ismir2011/paper/000011.pdf> (accessed 26 October 2025).

⁶⁹ <https://josquin.stanford.edu/> (accessed 26 October 2025).

⁷⁰ <https://www.tassomusic.org/> (accessed 26 October 2025).

⁷¹ <https://github.com/SEILSdataset/SEILSdataset> (accessed 26 October 2025).

The *1520s Project*, directed by Benjamin Ory and Craig Sapp, is another step ahead.⁷² Started in 2019, it contains around 500 music items from ca. 1510–40, encoded in MEI, MusicXML, MIDI, and Humdrum. The project features an exquisite and thorough treatment of the metadata and a sophisticated array of analytical tools.

Launched in 2023, *E-LAUTE* is the newest project in the field and one of the most ambitious. It aims to produce a comprehensive digital edition of lute tablatures written in German cypher. Supported by research agencies in Austria, Germany, and Switzerland, the project brings together a substantial interdisciplinary team under the leadership of Kateryna Schöning, Irene Holzer, and Martin Kirnbauer. The current focus is on tablatures dating from 1450 to 1550, with plans to extend coverage to works up to 1600 in subsequent phases, ultimately reaching a corpus of roughly 2,000 pages. The project demonstrates carefully considered choices in its use of technological standards (MEI and Web technologies), its balance between scholarly and performance-oriented perspectives, and its commitment to public engagement—most notably through opportunities for collaborative editing.⁷³

This progress represents a decisive move toward greater standardisation and accessibility in creating corpora, addressing the earlier fragmentation challenges. The importance of supporting as broad a range of formats as possible has been systematically articulated by Julie Cumming, Cory McKay, et al. in the aforementioned article.

Despite this general trend, a significant group of projects developed by Philippe Vendrix (Centre d'études supérieures de la Renaissance) and Richard Freedman (Haverford College) have taken a more focused approach, offering only MEI and PDF files. These include *The Lost Voices* (2012)⁷⁴ and *CRIM* (2018),⁷⁵ both of which are particularly strong on analysis. *Gesualdo Online* (2019), directed by Vendrix, exemplifies innovative dynamic editions.⁷⁶ Well-suited to their specific aims, the restricted choice of formats can pose challenges for interoperability, as converting MEI into other symbolic formats remains technically challenging.

Ideally, a digital corpus should consist of a representative selection of works curated for a specific scholarly objective, systematically edited and encoded per the established musicological conventions. It should provide PDF scores alongside symbolic files in as many formats as feasible, enriched with comprehensive metadata. This level of openness and structure not only enhances scholarly utility but also aligns with the FAIR principles:⁷⁷ making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable, thereby ensuring its long-term relevance and usability.

⁷² <https://1520s-project.org/about/> (accessed 26 October 2025).

⁷³ <https://e-laute.info/> (accessed 26 October 2025).

⁷⁴ <http://digitalduchemin.org/> (accessed 26 October 2025).

⁷⁵ <https://crimproject.org/> (accessed 26 October 2025).

⁷⁶ <https://ricercar.gesualdo-online.cesr.univ-tours.fr/> (accessed 26 October 2025).

⁷⁷ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/> (accessed 26 October 2025).

4.2 Aims and challenges of an analyst

Anna Plaksin

A key task for the analyst of a corpus is the mapping of the rationale present in the creation of a corpus with the goal of its interrogation. This is especially true when preexisting corpora of digital early music resources are reused and reaggregated. Data collections are gathered based on different goals, encompassing the spectrum of research-driven and curation-driven aims.⁷⁸ The role of a corpus in research can be understood as a model of the world we would like to gain knowledge of.

According to Herbert Stachowiak's definition, a model is always a representation of something. It generally captures not all the attributes of the original it represents, and it always represents the original not per se but for a specific context or under the restriction of certain operations.⁷⁹ Relying on this definition, this means that a corpus is always a representation of something in a different medium. It is not the original or a copy, it is a reduction. And it always aims at a special context – it only represents the original for a certain (limited) use. That means the re-use of a corpus in a different context is not guaranteed, and it is necessary to check whether the corpus and its assumptions fit the research question. Because both the creation rationales as well as the activities encompass nearly infinite possibilities.

Activities that involve the interrogation of early music corpora may be grouped into three categories:

1. Search / Retrieval: Finding resources by certain criteria.
E.g. finding teaching resources by composer, genre, or provenance or sheet music for performance for a certain setting, vocal range or difficulty.
These scenarios are mainly focused on metadata searches and aim at finding specific resources within a large collection.
2. Content-based analytical operations.
E.g. melodic search, automated music analysis or training an algorithm for automatic composition.
These activities need machine-readable representations of music. They do work fine with straightforward representations or modern transcriptions, e.g. as MIDI files, MusicXML or **kern.

⁷⁸ See J. Flanders and F. Jannidis, eds., *The Shape of Data in Digital Humanities: Modeling Texts and Text-Based Resources* (Routledge, 2019), 86–89.

⁷⁹ See H. Stachowiak, *Allgemeine Modelltheorie* (Springer, 1973), 131ff.

3. Content-based analytical operations focused on notation, sources and/or means of representation.
E.g. computational analysis of ornamentation in lute intabulations,⁸⁰ automatic collation and comparison of Renaissance polyphony,⁸¹ finding patterns in the visual appearance of Armenian Neumes⁸²
These activities are genuinely connected to the original notation in music sources. They do need representations that preserve features of the original notation and contain mechanisms to cope with notational idiosyncrasies and (editorial) interventions, including the documentation of such.

A key feature of early music research is its diversity. Regarding the analysis of early music corpora, this diversity is challenging but cannot be ignored. Based on the mentioned activities, four dimensions of diversity can be identified:

1. Different types of entities
Corpora can be collections of musical works, sources, modern editions or metadata.
2. Different representation
Representations may comprise digitised source images, uninterpreted original notation, interpreted digital notation - e.g. with applied imperfection and alteration, transcriptions into modern notation or modern (scholarly) editions.
3. Different notations
Early music covers a variety of music notations, e.g. chant, modal notation, mensural notation, common music notation, as well as lute, keyboard and other tablatures.
4. Different readers
Corpora can be presented and/or made accessible in many different ways.

There is hardly one corpus that fulfils every need. Therefore, the interrogation of early music corpora includes the evaluation of existing resources based on one's specific research goals. And the creation of corpora needs to take the diversity of questions and representations into account. As so often, this challenges the

⁸⁰ D. Lewis et al., 'Instrumental Idiom in the 16th Century: Embellishment Patterns in Arrangements of Vocal Music,' in *Proceedings of the 12th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference*, eds. M.I. Mandel et al. (2016): 524-530, <https://archives.ismir.net/ismir2016/paper/000165.pdf> (accessed 26 October 2026). The E-Laute project (<https://doi.org/10.55776/l6019>) is currently also working on methods for the computational analysis of German lute tablature.

⁸¹ A.V.K. Plaksin, 'Modelle zur computergestützten Analyse von Überlieferungen der Mensuralmusik: Empirische Textforschung im Kontext phylogenetischer Verfahren' (PhD diss., Technische Universität Darmstadt, 2021), <https://doi.org/10.26083/tuprints-00017211>.

⁸² E. De Luca and H. Utidjian, 'Challenging the MEI Neumes Module: Encoding Armenian Neumes,' in *Music Encoding Conference 2022 Proceedings*, eds. A.L. Ang et al. (2023), <https://doi.org/10.17613/gnnp-z327>.

relationship of 'the music' and its notation on a variety of levels. Whether a corpus should be interrogated about 'music', music documents or the practice of making, creating or writing music has an immediate effect on the entities being analysed. The analysis of counterpoint may be carried out on different material than the analysis of notational practices. Is it sufficient to treat different forms of notation as 'different shapes of notes and rests'? Should different music notations be compared to each other? Also, applied normalisation and emendation can have a significant impact on the suitability of a corpus for specific research areas.

Moreover, decisions made in the process of making a corpus accessible or when creating interfaces for querying or studying material involve many silent assumptions about the users of a collection: Is an entity in the corpus meant to be studied by a human eye or processed by a machine? Which features are meant to be processed or queried, and which features are meant to be looked at and studied by a human? How pervasive such assumptions are can be explained with a short example: an encoding has been created based on a publicly available digital image of a music source. One passage is purposefully notated in a very special way. For reasons not stated or unknown, maybe just because technology does not allow for it, the encoding normalises this passage and instead refers to the digital image of the encoded source. In such cases, the idiosyncratic notation is only available to an agent that can make sense of digital source images. This still implies the inspection of single cases by a human eye in close reading.

In summary, when working with corpora, any analysis and the interpretation of its results depend on the context of the corpus and its digital representation. Any finding in corpus-based research is only as good as the corpus allows. To make corpus-based research on early music feasible and inviting, we need strategies for navigating the aforementioned diversity. Currently, such strategies may comprise two areas: Documentation and automation.

Ideally, documentation makes the creation rationales of a corpus visible. It also reports on normalisation procedures, quality control, and describes the degree of heterogeneity. To enhance the findability and reusability of existing corpora and facilitate the (re-)aggregation of different corpora, this documentation is ideally available in a machine-readable form. Vital improvements for the interoperability of corpora can be achieved by improving processing and transformation capabilities. More sophisticated transformation procedures would allow the creation of derivatives and open a wide range of applications. Such derivatives do not necessarily need to be free of loss but should be possible to a certain degree and with a predictable loss of information. Finally, the further development of the existing ecosystem of software tools to support the creation of corpora in non-standard notation should also be a long-term goal. It should be easy to create, share and use high-quality corpora with the required metadata for academic use. Not just for experts but also for wider audiences.

4.3 Critical editing of music and the monumental/collected edition in the Digital Age

David J. Smith

Over recent decades there have been several exciting digital projects involving music notation. A few, such as the Josquin Research Project,⁸³ involved encoding collected editions, but most focused on diplomatic transcription of sources and the provision of digitized material online rather than engaging with critical editing. For example, Polish Digital Scores has involved diplomatic transcription of sources rather than the creation of critical editions: the aim has been to make available a significant corpus of encoded music, currently 8154 scores, rather than invest energy in making a smaller number of critical editions.⁸⁴ However, the boards of monumental editions throughout Europe are increasingly thinking about how to adapt – if at all – to the digital age.⁸⁵

Curiously, little progress has been made since Frans Wiering, Tim Crawford and David Lewis outlined the potential of a digital infrastructure for critical editions of music in 2009.⁸⁶ ‘Digital Directions for Collected Editions’ brought together musicologists specialising in critical editing, computer scientists, music technologists, librarians, computational musicologists and publishers to scope out what a collected edition of the future might look like in relation to three UK-based series, The Purcell Society Edition, Early English Church Music and Musica Britannica.⁸⁷ In a series of events from September 2021 to March 2023, it soon became apparent that the principal issue lay not in what was technologically possible but in questions of sustainability, both a sustainable financial model and questions surrounding the preservation of data and software maintenance (especially what happens after any funding runs out). The costs involved in creating digital editions are likely to be even greater than producing paper-based ones given

⁸³ <https://josquin.stanford.edu/about/> (accessed 26 October 2025).

⁸⁴ <https://polishscores.org/> (accessed 21 April 2025).

⁸⁵ A. Puentes-Blanco et al., ‘The Monumental Edition in the Digital Age: Creating a Sustainable Future,’ *Journal of New Music Research* 53, no. 3-4 (2024): 312-324, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09298215.2024.2373998>. Monumental editions of music include national collections demarcated by geography and collected editions defined by composer. They are generally well established, existing series producing volumes that typically may be found on the shelves of research libraries, although in many cases the intention of the series encompasses their use in performance too. ‘Monumental’ and ‘collected’ are often used interchangeably but in both cases imply that the editions are critical as well as scholarly.

⁸⁶ F. Wiering, ‘Digital Critical Editions of Music: A Multidimensional Model,’ in *Modern Methods for Musicology: Prospects, Proposals, and Realities*, eds. T. Crawford and L. Gibson (Ashgate, 2009): 23-46.

⁸⁷ AHRC-funded networking grant, ‘Digital Directions for Collected Editions’, grant number AH/V015095/1.

the need not only to develop sustainable software but also to create a corpus of data. The advantages of digital editions in terms of flexibility are precisely what makes them expensive: instead of the editor supplying one text of each piece, there is potentially the need for an encoding of each source of every piece. It became apparent both during 'Digital Directions' and in the EarlyMuse Short-Term Scientific Mission, CORSICA, that the answers to problems of sustainability lie in the fostering of user communities. Indeed, it was clear in discussions that there was no data on how (or even whether) existing monumental editions are used, and by whom.

Most musicians engage with music scores online, so in principle it should be possible to encourage interaction with scholarly, critical editions in the digital sphere. They expect to be able to locate material through a simple Google search, yet the metadata at item level for printed volumes in a series remains opaque - a search for a particular piece will bring up scores available on IMSLP,⁸⁸ or CPDL,⁸⁹ but not the collected edition containing it. This serves to highlight the importance of accurate metadata for encoded music generally and digital editions in particular. There is also an expectation that sheet music will be accessible via instant download, and at little or no cost. There is, therefore, friction between user expectation of free or cheap accessibility to sheet music and the cost of creating a scholarly, critical digital edition that requires the encoding of all sources for each piece.

With a collected or monumental edition, generally a user has to purchase an entire volume even if they need only one or two items from it. This contrasts with commercial websites such as musicnotes.com,⁹⁰ where the user pays a few dollars for what they actually want. For monumental editions of early music to survive, they need to be able to compete in ease of use and cost. Furthermore, the argument needs to be made for the intrinsic value of their scholarly worth.

The editing of seventeenth-century English keyboard music provides a useful case study. Communities of keyboard players are easier to identify and to nurture because they are made up of many individuals; these communities are also multifaceted, ranging from scholars to professional and amateur players, both organists and harpsichordists, and including teachers and students (including young learners who can realistically tackle simple pieces by Purcell and his contemporaries).⁹¹ Just as importantly, this repertoire circulated within a largely manuscript culture in which there are relatively few autograph manuscripts, and the ways in which scribes and users of manuscripts interacted creatively with the music

⁸⁸ International Music Score Library Project / Petrucci Music Library, <https://imslp.org/> (accessed 26 October 2025).

⁸⁹ Choral Public Domain Library, <https://www.cpdn.org/> (accessed 26 October 2025).

⁹⁰ <https://www.musicnotes.com/> (accessed 26 October 2025).

⁹¹ This lies at the heart of 'DigME - Digital Music Editions: Creating a Sustainable Future for the Monumental Edition', an (unsuccessful) follow-on AHRC grant application arising from 'Digital Directions', <https://gtr.ukri.org/projects?ref=AH%2FV015095%2F1> (accessed 8 September 2025).

The image displays a page of musical notation for Peter Philips's *Dolorosa Pavan*. The score is organized into multiple systems, each representing a different manuscript source. The sources listed on the left are: 3665, Lymar, PVB, Berl., Turin, 408, 9.33, 5.78, Fuhrmann, and Sch. The notation includes staves for treble and bass clefs, with various rhythmic values and accidentals. Key annotations include a box containing the number '26' at the top left, a note 'Top part added by second scribe' above the Berl. system, and several boxed references such as 'p. 227, I', 'f. 61v, I', and 'f. 18, iv'. The music features a mix of melodic lines and accompaniment, with some systems showing more complex rhythmic patterns.

Figure 6. Peter Philips, *Dolorosa Pavan*, parallel transcriptions (D.J. Smith, 'The Instrumental Music of Peter Philips' (PhD diss., University of Oxford, 1994) vol. 3, 97).

leads to a lack of fixity in the texts, which embed aspects of performance practice. If a digital infrastructure were to be developed that could cope with this repertory, then it would also be well-placed to deal with other genres and periods.

The issues facing someone creating a digital edition of music are the same as those involved for a paper-based one.⁹² Sources need to be collated and, in my view, each of them transcribed in full (Figure 6).

Figure 7. Peter Philips, *Dolorosa Pavan*, single text. © Copyright 1999 by The Musica Britannica Trust and Stainer & Bell Ltd. Reproduced from *Peter Philips: Complete Keyboard Music*, edited by David J. Smith, *Musica Britannica* Vol. 75 (p.125) by permission of Stainer & Bell Ltd, London, www.stainer.co.uk. All rights reserved.

In a printed edition, choices have to be made: a single text has to be established (Figure 7), and variance between sources encoded in a textual commentary – in the sort of algebraic shorthand seen in Figure 8. Note the inclusion of accurate metadata, such as the original titles of the piece and its location in its five keyboard sources; note also that the parallel transcriptions of it in Figure 6 include versions for consort and lute. Immediately, the potential of a digital platform to present this sort of information in a more digestible form becomes readily apparent.

There are two apparently conflicting approaches to the main text of a printed edition of early keyboard music: the first is to evaluate the sources and select one at the

⁹² For a discussion of the complexities involved in editing Purcell's keyboard music and how a digital edition of the future could open up new possibilities, see D.J. Smith and A. Woolley, 'Editing Purcell's Keyboard Music: Some Reflections on Collected Editions, Past and Future,' *Journal of New Music Research* 53, no. 3-4 (2024): 277-296, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09298215.2025.2472612>.

expense of the others; the second is to conflate the texts. However, in reality we are dealing with a spectrum with diplomatic transcription at one end and critical edition

15a DOLOROSA PAVAN

Ly, p.226: *Pavan dolorosa Pietro Philippi*.

Tr, p.152 (no.80): *Pauana Dolorosa. Treg. 11 †Peter Philips 1593*

Kr, f.6: *pauana dolorosa | Pauana dolorosa cōposta in prigione del d.º*

Tor, f.61: *Pauana Dolorosa* [anon.]

Dü, f.17v: *Paduana. Dolorosa. di. Pietro Philippi*.

This is an intabulation of a consort work contained in British Library, MS Egerton 3665, p.1022. The distribution of the notes follows Ly, which closely resembles Tr (in Kr the notes have only one possible location on the staves; the other two sources are in tablature). Tor and Dü occasionally add passing notes: these have not been recorded unless they occur in more than one source. In Dü, trill figures at cadences begin with a *q* on the note rather than with the upper auxiliary; in Tor they are usually indicated by an ornament sign. Unless otherwise indicated, double-stroke ornaments are taken from Ly.

1.b.1: orn. also in Tr/ 4.s.1: *Am* tied to ABCA *q*'s (Tor)/ 10.a.3: *b* from beginning of b.9 still holds (Ly & Tr) and is confirmed by reference to lute sources; *o* (Kr, Tor, Dü)/ 10.a.3 & b.1-2: Tor & Dü follow Kr/ 11.a.2: *Bb* (Kr)/ 12.a.2 & 13.a.1: *Bb* (Tr)/ 14.s.3-4: tied (Ly)/ 14.t.1-3: *Eq. Ddsq Edsq* for *Eq Fsq Esq* (Tr)/ 14.b.1: *mm* for *s* (Kr)/ 15.rh.1: chord ECA (Kr); chord CGE (Tor & Dü)/ 15.b.1: *Gm* for *Gs* (Ly); *G* orn. (Kr, Tor, Dü)/ 16.rh.1: chord GEC (Kr); CGE (Tor & Dü)/ 17.s: *c*-rest *Cm Cc* (Tor & Dü)/ 20.rh.6: *o* (Tr, Kr, Dü)/ 20.rh.12-15: GABC (Tr)/ 21.b.1: chord DG (Ly)/ 22.t.1: *mm*

for *s* (Tor)/ 25.rh: (Dü)/ 26.s.3: *o* (Ly;

Kr, Dü)/ 26.s.7-9: 3rd higher (Kr)/ 29.s.4: *Bb* (Tr)/ 29.s.10: *D* (Dü)/ 29.t.1-2: *DE* (Dü)/ 30.rh: Kr has rhythmically corrupt

Figure 8. Beginning of critical commentary for Peter Philips, *Dolorosa Pavan*. © Copyright 1999 by The Musica Britannica Trust and Stainer & Bell Ltd. Reproduced from *Peter Philips: Complete Keyboard Music*, edited by David J. Smith, *Musica Britannica* Vol. 75 (p.196) by permission of Stainer & Bell Ltd, London, www.stainer.co.uk. All rights reserved.

at the other. The conflation of sources is the norm for Musica Britannica volumes of keyboard music, and indeed for some seventeenth-century instrumental collections.⁹³ At the other end of the spectrum there are source-based editions such as the one of Fitzwilliam Virginal Book by Jon Baxendale and Francis Knights which, while scholarly in terms of its introductory material, is not critical – indeed, the editors

⁹³ For example, the Le Strange manuscripts, especially GB-Lbl, Add. MSS 39550-4, record every difference between his versions of music for viol consort and those in manuscripts owned by his friends, regardless of whether it affects how the music sounds. See *Peter Philips and Richard Dering: Consort Music*, ed. David J. Smith, *Musica Britannica* Vol. 101 (Stainer & Bell, 2016), xxiv-xxviii, 186-187.

describe it as a 'pseudo-facsimile',⁹⁴ and it preserves many graphical features of the manuscript, including the beaming of the shorter note-values and idiosyncratic notation of semibreves as two tied minims. The editors make minimal changes to the text, correcting obvious errors, and make suggestions concerning, for example, accidentals, but they do not refer to other sources of pieces contained in the Fitzwilliam Virginal Book: given the scale of the manuscript, this is understandable. The focus here is on the source, rather than on the composer.

Most editions sit somewhere in the middle of the spectrum: a source edition – as opposed to transcription – would correct obvious mistakes by reference to concordant sources; a composer edition usually has a main, principal, base text. Players have a use for both kinds of edition: here, for example, someone making a recording of Fitzwilliam Virginal book would need a source-based edition, but a concert of keyboard music by Peter Philips might require a composer-based one. An ideal edition, then, would be able to cater for both. However, traditional, paper-based publications cannot provide editions of all the sources alongside a critical edition combining them because of the constraints of space. This is where the dynamic, digital edition of the future comes in: the two editorial approaches can be reconciled, with source- and composer-editions coexisting in the same virtual space.

A critical edition needs to record all the information in one form or another, and the co-existence of source editions and composer editions makes this easier to achieve. During the STSM in Utrecht, we thought a great deal in terms of 'layers'. In the context of scholarly, critical music editions, encoding would involve a minimum of three levels, each building on the previous one:

- Diplomatic Source Transcription = Transparency: all sources should be encoded to produce diplomatic source transcriptions so that the user is able to refer back to the 'raw material'.
- Critical Source Editions: critical editions of the sources where the main text is changed only where absolutely necessary and by reference to the concordant sources.
- Critical Composer Editions: the focus is on the composer so, following the example of seventeenth-century sources such as the Le Strange consort manuscripts, a base text forms the foundation of an edition where there is greater flexibility in combining readings from different sources.

In the digital domain, such a multifaceted edition could follow the model of existing collected editions: at a click of a mouse, the textual commentary could appear but using music notation rather than text. Notes could be coloured on screen to alert the user to disagreement between sources. However, it would also be feasible to display texts in parallel in a manner not dissimilar to Figure 6, or to use IIIF⁹⁵ to create links

⁹⁴ *The Fitzwilliam Virginal Book*, eds. J. Baxendale and F. Knights (Lyrebird Music, 2020) vol. 1, xxxi.

⁹⁵ International Image Interoperability Framework, <https://iiif.io/> (accessed 26 October 2025).

between a bar in the edition and the corresponding place on a digitized image of the source.⁹⁶ The latter is more easily envisaged for source editions, and has been implemented in some of the Polish scores: see, for example, Giovanni Matteo Asola's *Ave Sanctissima Maria* where double-clicking on a note brings up an image of the corresponding system in its source. The same piece may be used to illustrate how digital editions can facilitate the co-existence of original and modern notation: on the click of a mouse the display may be changed from original clefs, note-values (including stemming), part-names, spelling and orthography to a modern score of modern clefs, with barlines added, modern part-names, spelling and orthography. Different users of sheet keyboard music have different priorities, and there is disagreement over the extent to which graphical aspects of the notation (such as the beaming of quavers and semiquavers) have implications for performance practice. A digital edition would therefore be able to take the user from a version with original notation (number of staff lines, clefs, beaming, placement of accidentals) to a modern one. There could be similar options for downloading PDFs for printing or use on a tablet.

For a digital edition along the lines suggested above to be possible, there is a need for corpus creation. All texts for each piece need to be encoded and ideally the entire contents of each manuscript so that the edition becomes a research tool to explore scribal interaction with the music. A digital edition such as is being proposed here shifts the focus away from composers and on to scribes and users of manuscripts in the seventeenth century. On the face of it, IIF links to images might suggest that not everything needs to be encoded. However, a player who believes that beaming of smaller note values is indicative of phrasing would want it preserved in a source edition. System-breaks can be vital to understanding placement of accidentals and can provide valuable evidence of inter-source relationships. Furthermore, anything that remains within a digitised image of a source without being encoded becomes 'invisible' to a machine and therefore makes the data less useful when analysing the music. One significant advantage of a scholarly digital edition is that it can be more than the visual presentation of musical notation: the data required for the creation of a multidimensional, dynamic edition as envisaged above can be manipulated for a range of other purposes. Whereas a research project involving a particular research question may involve making compromises in what to include, leaving out any elements that will not be needed in addressing it, a digital edition needs to remain as open and flexible as possible since it needs to meet the needs of a range of users. As part of the Utrecht STSM, a number of interviews were conducted (see Section 7.1), and one participant commented that 'you don't know what it is that you need to know until you need to know it'. A monumental edition need not have a specific goal in mind, so needs to involve

⁹⁶ <https://polishscores.org/?id=16xx:900> (accessed 26 October 2025).

encoding as much as possible in order to make it useful to the widest range of audiences.

Manually encoding music from scratch is labour-intensive. However, the use of existing digital material speeds things up immeasurably. Any existing transcription or edition of a piece can serve as the basis: OMR can be used if necessary to create a Music XML file that can then be tidied up in a notation software package before being exported as XML and converted to MEI. The Music XML file can be edited multiple times to generate the various layers needed for a dynamic digital edition. However, it is still a mammoth effort, especially if the encoding is to include the degree of detail suggested. There is a trade-off to be made between speed and quantity on the one hand and inclusivity on the other. Some projects have involved the beneficiaries – the user communities – in the creation of a resource, but this raises issues of Intellectual Property and copyright when working with established series, not to mention quality assurance.

During the STSM, Mark Gotham gave an illuminating presentation on encoding German Lieder and string quartets. Although the repertoire is later, we benefited from his experience in crowd-sourcing the encoding of nineteenth-century editions which seemed to have been highly successful. By using such editions as sources, he avoided issues of IP and copyright. However, Julie Cuming and Cory McKay reflected on their projects, including ELVIS and SIMSSA. Their experience of crowd-sourced encodings of music which were intended primarily for analysis differed markedly from that of Mark mainly because the sources used as their basis varied: some encodings employed reduced note values whereas others did not. They were sceptical about using crowdsourcing for the creation of encoded corpora of music and preferred smaller but accurate and consistent datasets to larger ones. The contrast between the two perspectives illustrated the trade-off between quality and scale. A project involving the creation of a new series of critical editions might well involve users in their creation. Ironically, the lack of lute music in monumental editions such as *Musica Britannica* has led to the creation of digital resources by enthusiasts which can now provide the source transcriptions needed for critical editions of, for example, lute music by Dowland.⁹⁷ However, the issues of IP and copyright are that much greater for a well-established monumental edition, especially when new editions are made from existing material. In the case of existing series, there is scope to involve user communities in the design of a future digital critical edition.

It may be unrealistic to expect a user necessarily to pay for an edition if they have contributed to its creation. This is perhaps where there needs to be a distinction between data and edition: an encoded manuscript is a digital representation of our

⁹⁷ T. Crawford, 'A Digital Corpus for Exploring the Lute Music of John Dowland (1563–1626),' *Journal of New Music Research* 53, no. 3–4 (2025): 1–11, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09298215.2025.2486139>.

shared heritage so perhaps should not be monetized, whereas an edition arising from it is invested with the intellectual property of whoever created it. Clearly, were crowdsourcing to be used for encoding texts in the creation of a critical edition for an established series, there would need to be absolute transparency surrounding the arrangement.

There is an obvious need to be able to combine data for editions of English keyboard music made by several individual editors or editorial teams, especially when one is working on a composer, and another on an individual source. For scholarly, critical editions of keyboard music to flourish in the digital sphere, there needs to be a degree of standardisation, consistency and transparency. In the longer term, however, it is possible to envisage combining datasets of this keyboard repertoire with those of other kinds of music – maybe traditional, folk music? – to explore broader questions of dissemination and transmission.

4.4 How to select a representative corpus for historical study

Mirjam Visscher and Frans Wiering

The first problem one encounters when doing corpus-based music research is the creation of the corpus itself, for the composition of the corpus is a critical factor in the validity of the research outcomes. A suitable corpus minimally meets the following criteria:

- it fits the research question: it must contain the features that are relevant to the research;
- it is representative of the music under investigation, in terms of spread over different strata such as genre, country and composers.

The latter problem is the topic of this section. It seems that most of the corpus research (insofar as it doesn't study a closed corpus, such as the complete output of a composer) uses an approach of convenience sampling, making the most of the available data sets and/or the (usually limited) amount of time for data creation. We are not aware of a solid method to select compositions for inclusion in a musical corpus. However, in computational linguistics a comprehensive, straightforward method has been defined by Biber, that can be transferred to the music domain.⁹⁸

Biber's approach has three important steps:

- define the boundaries of the population;
- define the organisation within the population;
- set a sampling frame.

We will illustrate this approach with a short example. For this we define the boundaries of the population as all western music surviving in manuscript or print dated between 1500 and 1700. The organisation within the population refers to

⁹⁸ D. Biber, 'Representativeness in Corpus Design,' *Literary and linguistic computing* 8, no. 4 (1993): 243-257, <https://doi.org/10.1093/lc/8.4.243>.

properties known as *strata* such as the composer, genre, secular or sacred nature, instrumentation, country, language and date. The choice of strata relates to the research question: a representative corpus reflects the distribution of compositions over the selected strata of the population.

Figure 9. Conceptual population breakdown of all music there ever was (dark blue) into the partially overlapping categories known (yellow), known & lost (red) and underrepresented (green). The visible dark blue area represents the unknown repertoire, of which we do not know its size.

Figure 9 shows that the population has some problematic aspects. First, it is already a selection from all western music there ever was in the 16th and 17th centuries. We know very substantial amounts of music were lost. In some cases, we know that compositions and sources existed in the past, but there is an unknown amount of music that has vanished without a trace. There is no reason to assume that this was a purely random process in which every piece stood the same chance of surviving, so we can be sure this has influenced the distributions of strata. There is some specialised research into the estimation of numbers of items lost without a trace,⁹⁹ but we are not aware of methods for doing so at a large scale.¹⁰⁰ Information on the known losses is scattered over the literature: it would be helpful if a centralised inventory of these could be created. A second problematic aspect is the occurrence

⁹⁹ M.S. Cuthbert, 'Tipping the Iceberg: Missing Italian Polyphony from the Age of Schism,' *Musica Disciplina* 54 (2009): 39-74, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25750547>; M. Kestemont, et al., 'Forgotten Books: The Application of Unseen Species Models to the Survival of Culture,' *Science* 375, issue 6582 (2022): 765-769, <https://www.doi.org/10.1126/science.abl7655>.

¹⁰⁰ Recently, however, it was estimated how many Gregorian chants have disappeared, based on the chant distributions in the CANTUS database (<https://cantusdatabase.org/>, accessed 30 October 2025): J. Hajič, jr. and F.C. Moss, 'Knowing When to Stop: Insights from Ecology for Building Catalogues, Collections, and Corpora,' in *DLfM '25: Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Digital Libraries for Musicology*, ed. E. De Luca (Association for Computing Machinery, 2024): 90-94, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3748336.3748347>.

of anonymous compositions. This is not a negligible category: in RISM, 18% of the items are anonymous and in CPDL 10% of the compositions are anonymous. Anonymous works are often hard to date, and their geographical origin may also be less easy to identify. The distribution of anonymous composers is not uniform geographically; we know for instance that the majority of 17th century Scottish compositions are by an anonymous composer.¹⁰¹ They thus pose a serious problem to creating a representative selection.

Third, not taking underrepresented groups into account may introduce additional bias. There are catalogues of music by underrepresented groups, such as the ones in Table 2. Such lists aren't the final answer, however, since the attention for the underrepresented may lead to overrepresentation and other underrepresented groups may be missing. Being explicit about such problems, even if they cannot be solved, is the best strategy.

category	dataset name	url
Iberian polyphony	Archive of Iberian Polyphony	https://iberianpolyphony.fcsh.unl.pt/
Female composers	BIG LIST of Women Composers	https://donne-uk.org/the-big-list/
Spanish and New World Polyphony	Books of Hispanic Polyphony	https://hispanicpolyphony.eu
Poland, 16th-20th century	Polish digital scores	https://polishscores.org/
Spanish Renaissance	Tomás Luis de Victoria	https://www.uma.es/victoria/index.html

Table 2. Sample catalogues of underrepresented groups.

The third and last step in Biber's methodology is creating a sample frame. Such a frame consists of one or more lists with attributes and their distribution over the population. Table 3 gives two simple examples of sample frames creating from RISM.

In practice sample frames will be hierarchical (for example genre and country). After the sampling frame has been created, the actual corpus can be selected by randomly choosing compositions that fill the 'slots' in the frame. How many need to be selected depends on the minimum number of pieces per slot. In the end, we have a sample that is substantially smaller than the population but nevertheless is representative of it by the chosen criteria.

¹⁰¹ D. Coney, 'The David Melville Bassus Partbook and Scottish Music Culture at the Turn of the 17th Century,' paper presented at the International Medieval and Renaissance Music Conference, Durham, U.K, July 2025.

composer	%	genre	%
Anonymous	18.1	Sacred song	12.9
Palestrina	0.7	Opera	7.1
Lassus	0.4	Lied	4.4
Lully	0.3	Motet	4.0
Purcell	0.2	Song	3.7
Marenzio	0.1	Keyboard piece	3.6
Byrd	0.1	Mass	3.4
Victoria	0.1	Sonata	3.1
Gallus	0.1	Aria	3.1
Frescobaldi	0.1	Cantata	3.0

Table 3. Sampling frames for composers and genres based on the RISM records (top 10).

5 Beyond the scholarly community

As has been repeatedly suggested in the previous chapters, the involvement of contributors from outside the scholarly community to corpus creation (in the widest sense) is quite important. Where possible the connection between music researchers, professional musicians and citizen scientists deserves to be fostered. Section 5.1 illustrates this by means of an analysis of the contributions to CPDL, a major online resource of choral music. In Section 5.2 digital editing is studied as a collaborative process where contributors are motivated to perform certain tasks: these tasks should be designed in such a way that they reduce technical complexity and allow focus on the musical task at hand.

5.1 CPDL contributors: a case study

Mirjam Visscher and Frans Wiering

Early 2024, we investigated the productivity of the contributors by scraping the contents of the site. At the time 60,868 editions of works by 4,753 composers were available. As our focus is on corpus building and reusability of encodings, we looked into the prevailing file format for sharing encodings, MusicXML. Our dataset contains 48,847 MusicXML files by 1,609 contributors, accompanied by metadata.

Figure 10. Top 25 CPDL contributors (anonymised) and the years during which they were active. The contributors account for 69% of the total number of 48,874 MusicXML files contributed to CPDL.

First, we looked into activity and productivity of the top 25 contributors. Their efforts account for 33,836 files or 69% of the total number of MusicXML files (see Figure 10).

Figure 11. Productivity metrics over the years.

Figure 11 shows how over time new contributors joined the CPDL platform and that the long-term trend for the number of pieces added per year is going upward while the average productivity of the contributions seems stable. From a business economics perspective, these metrics are a sign of healthy continuity.

Figure 12. Composition years (smoothed) of the contributions by the top 10 CPDL contributors (anonymised).

Figure 12 documents the historical focus of the top 10 contributors. Most contributors show a preference for either Renaissance/Baroque or Classical/Romantic compositions, while only one of them (contributor c1) is strongly active in both repertoires. If we look into overall productivity (Figure 13), another smaller peak emerges for contemporary works. For the purpose of this report, however, it is important to signal that a very substantial proportion of all encodings concern early music. This makes it worthwhile to investigate if and how these encodings could be made available for corpus-based research.

Figure 13. Quarter-century of composition of all MusicXML contributions. The date of each composition is naively estimated as the average of the years of birth and death of the composer, allowing only a high-level impression.

5.2 Participation and collaboration in corpus creation

David Lewis and David Weigl

Collaborative practices are common in the creation of music corpora. Splitting the effort of digitizing, typesetting, encoding, or validating a corpus permits projects to scale in different directions: in the number of pieces or pages processed; in the complexity of the music tackled; in the level of quality assurance that may be provided; and in the size of the audience that may be reached with the results of the effort. Collaborations may be undertaken by colleagues within a company or institution; by collaborators across institutions; by members of communities, such as music appreciation societies or performance groups; or, by volunteers brought together in crowd-sourcing efforts, perhaps unknown to one another but sharing a desire to contribute.

Digital music corpora are created for a variety of reasons, and collaborative actions are driven by a number of different incentives. Contributors may be incentivized by external factors - most clearly, remuneration or contractual obligation - but their work may also be driven, in part or entirely, by inherent incentives. Particularly where these in themselves drive individuals to seek to contribute to corpus creation projects without prompting, one may speak of 'self-incentivization'. A potent motivating factor is the prospective utility that the resulting resources would have to the individuals - for instance, members of an orchestra or choir may be incentivized

to collaboratively encode performance part scores of their repertoire, where these are otherwise unavailable or where performance rights would be prohibitively expensive to acquire. Similarly, contributors may be motivated by the perceived utility of the resources to themselves or other community members, or to wider society – for instance, to preserve cherished cultural heritage. In certain cases, particularly in cross-institutional collaborations and where efforts are motivated by a wider audience, projects may choose public licenses for their outputs, further increasing the utility of their work to others. Beyond purely altruistic intent, contributors may derive a sense of social interaction and of community belonging from such pursuits, particularly where the various acts of collaboration include discussion and exchange. Certainly, this has driven significant contributions to prior projects.

It is likely these outward facing aspects of community and wider cultural impact that drive certain rare individuals to especially significant efforts: contributions to successful crowd-sourcing efforts typically follow power-law distributions, both broadly (e.g., [Wikipedia](#)¹⁰²) and in music (e.g., [MusicBrainz](#),¹⁰³ [OpenScore](#)¹⁰⁴). In other words, a scant few people typically contribute a hugely disproportionate amount of voluntary effort to such projects, whereas many others fill out the ‘long tail’ of contributions. It will be helpful to large crowd-sourcing efforts in music to understand the specific motivations of their potential ‘super’ volunteers.

In music corpus creation, ‘digitisation’ may occur at different levels of complexity with differing requirements and technical affordances for collaborative work. On one end of the spectrum, documents bearing physical notation may be scanned or photographed, and distributed as images. This process is largely generic for any document type, whether text, music or illustrations, and relatively fast, making mass digitisation technically and practically simple. Similarly, the documents produced, whether jpegs or PDFs can be viewed using generic tools, with no need for music-specific software. Comprehension of the symbols is then left to the literacy and paleographic skill of the readers. As the digitised resources are not machine-interpretable and directly obtained through interaction with physical resources, it is very difficult to collaborate at scale in the digitisation of a collection in this way.

¹⁰² S. Javanmardi et al., ‘User Contribution and Trust in Wikipedia,’ in *Proceedings of the 5th International ICST Conference on Collaborative Computing: Networking, Applications, Worksharing*, eds. J. Joshi and T. Zhang (2009), <https://doi.org/10.4108/icst.collaboratecom2009.8376>.

¹⁰³ J. Hemerly, ‘Making Metadata: The Case of MusicBrainz,’ (master’s thesis, University of California, Berkeley, 2009), https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1982823 (accessed 27 October 2025).

¹⁰⁴ M. Gotham et al., ‘Scores of Scores: An Openscore Project to Encode and Share Sheet Music,’ in *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Digital Libraries for Musicology*, ed. K. Page (Association for Computing Machinery, 2018): 87-95. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3273024.3273026>

On the other extreme, MEI, the comprehensive, XML-based schema for score descriptions developed by the Music Encoding Initiative, is technically complex and not hugely practical for most music performers, with its emphasis on music semantics over layout and with few user-facing tools; but its musically-informed hierarchical structure makes it highly amenable to collaborative edition processes. For instance, defining score fragments (pages, systems, parts, measures...) to be farmed out in encoding or validation tasks to large groups of users is relatively straightforward, whilst editorial interventions or disagreements can be clearly represented with indications of the provenance of each decision. Other formats can provide more practical, but less comprehensive, options. Notable among these for community projects are MusicXML (which can be created by a variety of popular applications), ABC (which offers simple, human-readable syntax) and MuseScore's proprietary format (favoured partly because of the free and open nature of the software).

The level of openness in the licensing and development of tools and formats used in collaboration forms another important consideration. While the tools producing MusicXML tend to be more practical in their usage - requiring less technical expertise - they are restricted in the features they can offer by the scope and relative fixity of the format. Further, as MusicXML is generally used for interchange after conversion from a proprietary format, minor editorial changes may result in significantly different MusicXML outputs. On the other hand, MEI is developed by the open community of the Music Encoding Initiative, making it feasible to introduce changes or new additions (e.g., to cover different notation types). The MEI community is particularly interested in editorial work and early music, and as a result is well suited to notations beyond CMN and for scholarly applications.

Further, though fewer user-friendly tools are available for working with MEI, those that are - e.g. Oxygen, mei-friend¹⁰⁵ - emphasise the use of distributed code versioning technologies such as git (itself open-source software), strongly supporting the robustness and viability of collaborative edition processes. Of course, this in turn carries requirements in terms of technical expertise. A broader consideration must be undertaken in the context of collaborative corpus generation: different obstacles to participation, in terms of musicological, musical, and technical literacy, must be overcome in what is inherently a highly interdisciplinary process. On the one hand, lowering these barriers should be a primary criterion in the development of methods and tooling for this purpose. On the other, the requirement for assembling groups of collaborators with differing and complementary expertise must be considered by those engaging in collaborative corpus-creation efforts, as a necessary precursor to success.

¹⁰⁵ W. Goebel and D.M. Weigl, 'mei-friend: An Interactive Web-Based Editor for Digital Music Encodings,' *Journal of Open Source Software* 9, no. 98 (2024): 6002, <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.06002>.

6 Early music encoding: a PACT analysis

6.1 Brief introduction to PACT

In this chapter we will integrate some of the findings from the previous chapters in order to create an overview of the dimensions and human factors involved in corpus creation. We will use the PACT framework for this. This framework, developed in Interactive Systems Design, is meant for the exploration of a design situation by means of four main dimensions (which are subsequently developed), namely People, Activities, Contexts and Technologies.¹⁰⁶

Figure 14. The PACT dimension and their interrelationships (after Benyon, *Designing User Experience*, 110).

Figure 14 shows how these are related: People use Technologies to perform Activities in a given Context. For example: a musician uses MuseScore to create an edition for a concert. Ideally, human and technology merge into a 'People-Technology system' that seamlessly executes the work. Organising exploratory information using PACT may for example help to identify areas for further exploration and questions to be asked to stakeholders; trace tensions and contradictions to be addressed; and suggest some initial requirements.

The order of the four dimensions isn't just dictated by the acronym but was intentionally chosen so that human aspects come first and technologies last (logically not in time).¹⁰⁷ The implication is that technologies are studied in the context of their intended use. In this respect it is maybe surprising that PACT treats content (in our case, music) as an aspect of technologies. This should be understood as an analysis

¹⁰⁶ Benyon, *Designing User Experience*, Chapter 2.

¹⁰⁷ Software design is usually seen as an iterative not a linear process.

of the properties of the content that the technologies must be able to deal with. Again, it makes sense to do so in relation to the design problem, which in turn depends on the aims of the people involved. The four PACT dimensions are thus intimately connected, and it is not unusual for a design issue to be related to more than one dimension.

6.2 People

People involved in encoding and editing music display much diversity along multiple dimensions. Some are professional musicians or music researchers, others software engineers and computer scientists, but there is also a large contingent of amateur workers who at times are extremely productive, maybe even more so than most professionals. Many amateurs reach a quite high level of musical expertise – and can thus be regarded as fully-fledged citizen scientists – while others only possess an elementary knowledge of music. Likewise technical expertise varies much, from just being able to work with simple music editing programs, via mastery of certain software (which may even include hacking the system to create the desired score features) to the ability to create encoding systems, software and online ecosystems. Few people seem to possess the full range of interdisciplinary expertise that the field requires, which means that collaboration is a necessity but also that tensions may arise between workers, reflecting their different disciplinary values. An example of this could be the musician’s attention to specific notational details versus the software engineer’s generalisation in modelling notation. Finally, there is the workers’ roles to consider: both ‘makers’ and ‘users’ are part of the ecosystem. Users include music corpus researchers, but also musicians, who may need editions tailored for specific tasks or circumstances, and even machines can assume the role of users (see Section 4.2).

Workers have different aims and values. We have already encountered the distinction between aims in the field of corpus analysis, such as studying historical developments and in digital editing. The former seems primarily a professional aim, while the latter attracts a much wider demography. Editing can be a primarily scholarly activity, but editing for performance (whether amateur or professional) seems to be the dominant aim. An extension of this seems to be editing for the love of music, often resulting in a systematic production of encodings and editions.

Sharing and giving something in return to the community also seem to be important drivers. With sharing comes the question of what to format to share in, which relates to control over the content, and recognition for the effort. It is important to keep such values in mind when contemplating corpus creation models that ingest and process work of others at scale. Another relevant value is autonomy, the freedom to choose music and the way to encode/edit it. Individual projects offer most freedom (though at the expense of scale), and centralised projects the least (but can be more productive). Community projects occupy a medium position, combining a given

infrastructure and easy access to expertise with considerable freedom in the realisation of personal aims.

6.3 Activities

Here we again make a distinction between the roles of ‘makers’ and ‘users’ of encodings.

Given a maker’s aims, the first group of activities is about making choices:

- choosing the music: a single work, a sample (whether striving for representativity or not), or a complete set (for example a whole source, the repertoire of an institution, the output of a composer);
- choosing the exemplar(s) to work from, whether historical sources or modern editions
- choosing which musical properties to encode and which to ignore, and/or which editorial methods and encoding guidelines to follow;
- choosing encoding systems and file formats;
- choosing the tools for the working and publication environment.

Many of these choices are interdependent and balancing them is not a trivial task, making starting a project from scratch a daunting endeavour.

Another series of activities relates to the production process and include: entering the score into the computer; checking the encoded score for completeness, errors and consistency with guidelines; conversion to delivery formats; publication; adding metadata; and documenting the work. Alternatively, production process may start with the ingestion of existing encodings or OMR output. The production activities may be carried out by a single person, but more commonly multiple workers are involved.

From the perspective of the user and their aims, the first step is again about making choices:

- choosing the music (which again may require a sampling strategy);
- choosing the musical properties that are needed for the aim;
- finding available resources encodings that match the above;
- evaluating the quality of the selected encodings;
- choosing the tools for processing the encodings;
- converting the encodings to a format that the tools can process.

Again, choices are interdependent, and it may well be the case that compromises must be made, for example with respect to the selection of music. The outcome may also be that the data are missing essential features or that the quality is not good enough, necessitating an excursion to the ‘maker’ workflow to further enrich the encodings. Ideally, the output of this excursion is fed back to the creators of the encodings and integrated in their materials.

The processing of the data depends on the kind of desired output, with two main categories, analytical results or music. The former entails the use of specialised music software such as music21, software for machine learning or data analysis such as WEKA, or generic program languages such as Python. Music as output implies the ability to perform tasks such as conversion to CMN, transposition, choosing types of editorial detail, adaptation to performance circumstances, and sonification.

Both user and maker perspectives spawn an extended workflow of tasks that differ in complexity and expertise needed. In principle, it seems possible to split these up in subtasks that can be carried out by workers with the right combination of qualities. However, even the simplest tasks are likely to require accuracy, concentration, and understanding of the content. Therefore, it is crucial to design user interfaces in such a way that they optimally support the task at hand and do not distract or hinder it, in other words, with full attention to usability aspects that are sadly often ignored.

6.4 Contexts

Three types of context are distinguished in the PACT model: physical environment, social context, and organisational context. Considering the first, most of the work probably takes place in offices, libraries and home studies using a desktop computer. As an alternative setting one might think of a mobile device, on which micro tasks can be executed in a collaborative scenario, for example when travelling by public transport or while waiting in a queue. This would require a completely different approach to task and interface design.

In terms of social context, most workers, even if they do their editing and encoding in isolation, are part of a community of practice (for example Lilypond) that shares the same tools and publication platforms and where they can ask each other for help. When designing a new corpus creation project, it is imperative not only to focus on tools and tasks, but to actively design and foster the social environment in which the work takes place as well. If workers don't feel connected, supported and valued, they will go elsewhere.

Organisational context brings in several interrelated factors that influence the long-term success of a project:

- organisational embedding: projects are generally short-term, but are they endorsed and supported by organisations with a longer lifespan?
- storage: where are the data hosted, how are they backed up?
- technical sustainability: will data and interface for accessing them remain available and if necessary updated after the project?
- intellectual sustainability: are sustainable formats used and is there documentation that records provenance of the data and encoding decisions, so that future users understand the potential and limitations of the data?
- financial sustainability: what does it cost to maintain the environment and how is income generated to do so?

Other organisational factors include:

- intellectual property: can data be lawfully shared, and is everyone's share in creating them adequately recognised?
- relation to other initiatives, such as digitisation projects of libraries and archives, cataloguing endeavours (RISM, CANTUS, DIAMM), and division of labour with related projects;
- interoperability with the Linked Open Data world, for example by means of shared identifiers for various entities like persons and compositions;
- observation of FAIR principles.

The subtext here is that, although crowdsourcing and employing citizen scientists seem like cheap strategies to assemble a lot of data, corpus creation remains an expensive activity in a world where funding for cultural heritage and humanities research is scarce. When available, funding needs to be spent wisely and effectively, and when not available, strong and at the same time realistic cases need to be made to funding agencies to convince them that music corpus creation is a worthy destination for their money.

6.5 Technologies

In the PACT framework, Technologies are divided in four categories, input, output, communication and content. We will skip input and communication,¹⁰⁸ important though they may be, since at this rather generic level of PACT analysis, little can be said about these that is specific to our problem. This is different for output, as this category describes the variety of products that corpus creation may aim at. Briefly summarised, the following dimensions have been identified:

- data oriented to edition oriented encoding;
- selective to near-complete encoding, with the qualification that complete encoding is unattainable and a well-articulated decision must be made about where to stop;
- encodings and editions range from source-oriented to composer-oriented approaches;
- whether symbols (e.g. ligatures) or semantics (e.g. pitches and durations) are encoded;
- the notation output can be static, allow basic manipulation such as reformatting or selection of voices, or can be dynamic, affording notation-altering manipulations such as transcription and transposition;
- whether the intended medium for the end product is paper or digital;
- reusability of the encodings, ranging from none to basic features to complete encodings.

¹⁰⁸ Input is mainly about input devices. For our purpose one could think of scanners and (music) keyboards as non-standard input devices. Communication addresses matters such as network connections, protocols, and transmission speed.

This range of output options implies a corresponding range of technical decisions in the design of the musical content. Such decisions take the form of computational models, abstract structures that capture aspects of the music in a formal logical structure. As explained in 4.2, a model is a reduction of the original for a certain purpose, and it is important to understand what is included in the model as well as what isn't. Aspects of corpus creation that relate to content and modelling are:

- encoding system(s) used in the system; conversion
- quality and accuracy of the encoding
- notation form of the source (mensural, tablature, CMN)
- choice of features to encode
- inclusion of digital images (potentially linking of image and encoding via IIIF)
- metadata format describing source and encoding process

Metadata design in particular seems an underdeveloped area: the choice seems to be in practice to either use a minimalistic approach and supply little beyond composer and title, or work with a verbose format such as the TEI/MEI header. There is a need for developing a middle ground, where metadata profiles are defined for specific repertoires but that can still be shared at a higher level.

6.6 Conclusion

This PACT analysis can have multiple purposes. It can serve as a framework to describe current projects, identify opportunities for improving them, compare them and find chances for collaboration or data exchange. It can also be seen as a set of questions and attention points for designers of future music corpus creation environments that they can use as a starting point for user research and requirements gathering.

An important generic observation about all PACT dimensions is that accurate documentation, not just of the specific encoding task but of the entire project, is vital, otherwise the user of the project output is left in the dark with respect to factors that fundamentally shape the encodings. Such documentation should include:

- musical documentation, describing the aim and content of the project, as well as criteria for inclusion/exclusion of compositions;
- technical documentation about the system design and implementation;
- maker documentation, explaining the creation workflow in the system;
- user documentation, explaining how the encodings can be manipulated: it should also discuss design choices and limitations that may influence the interpretation of the outcomes;
- metadata documentation, explaining how the encoding should be formally described.

In all documentation it is vital not just to present all the options (which sadly is what most user manuals document) but to give task oriented, practical advice that matches the problem the encoder is struggling with.

7 Narrowing the gulf between people and systems in music encoding

In our activities, we focused on the people involved in the creation and use of corpora in three ways, interviews (Section 7.1), the creation of personas (Section 7.2), and the analysis of roles in collaborative corpus creation (Section 7.3).

7.1 Interviews

We conducted nine interviews, six with musicologists and three with citizen scientists, to learn more about encoders' motivations and experiences. We present a short overview of their responses.

Multiple respondents mention that discovery is an important *motivation* for their work, as is sharing their discoveries with others. Another motivation is altruism: doing something for other musicologists or performers, or giving back to the community in exchange for the use of other people's materials. Other motivations include obsessive collecting, editing as a way of gaining deep knowledge of the music, inaccessibility of expensive scholarly editions, and leaving something behind for future generations. All respondents see *PDF* as the primary format for distribution, though several mention *sharing encodings*; one of them does not want to share encodings for fear of others interfering with their work. There are some interesting thoughts though on the *added value of digital editions*, such as support for multiple completions of the same work (from an interviewee working with polyphony fragments), better visibility of sources in the edition, different 'viewpoints' on the edition for different user groups, searching for intertextual relationships, support for annotation, and finally quantitative analysis.

Respondents generally expect *acknowledgment of their work* and appreciate feedback on their scores. No one expects material reward, but some would have a problem with their work being re-used in a commercial setting and have licenced their work accordingly. Some respondents plan to share their work at a later stage and wonder about the right platform to do so. One quite interesting suggestion is to *create a centralised place* (irreverently described as a 'dumpster') where researchers could deposit their encodings for others to use, after having finished researching them.

Quality is a major concern for all. Everyone works directly from primary sources (we know that many encoders work from modern editions, but not our respondents) and aims to create accurate scores. *Better access to sources* is desirable, especially to underrepresented materials such as organ tablatures. Generally, they apply *guidelines or principles*, formally or informally. Such principles can be very concise ('reversibility, traceability, transparency') and sometimes evolve over time. Sometimes formal guidelines are followed. Critical commentaries range from none

to very extensive texts. One respondent suggests a peer approval process for contributions to CPDL-like resources.

Our respondents come from several *communities of practice* (e.g. Humdrum, MEI, Lilypond, MuseScore, Finale, digital lutenists) and seem to be generally happy with the functionalities that their platform offer, minor complaints excepted. At times they mention limitations of other platforms. Technical help seems to be mostly available, and the citizen scientists have easy access to musicological expertise. It is not uncommon for digitised sources and unpublished transcriptions to be shared with peers. One participant is involved in a large-scale funded project and works with multiple colleagues. Others work individually and rather interact with their communities on an ad-hoc basis.

7.2 Personas

Anna Plaksin and Frans Wiering

We also used our experiences to create personas - fictional representations of potential users - each with a short profile including biographic background, experiences, motivations, and frustrations. This should help us to create a shared understanding of potential communities and a shared vision for the future of corpus building. In teams of two, we created five different personas with varying backgrounds. We envisioned people between their early 20s and their mid-70s, some of them professional musicians, others music enthusiasts with varying aspirations. Envisioned experiences, motivations, and frustrations were already astonishingly diverse, ranging from seeking material to play from, community, visibility of their own work, and recognition (for a compact survey see Table 4).

However, the effect of creating these personas did not lie so much in their details but in their impact on our discussions. Motivations and frustrations of potential users increasingly guided our decisions and led us to take the consequences of design choices into account. It contrasted our earlier mapping of the many modalities of creating or using digital corpora of early music by giving us a perspective from within this system, showing potential considerations for choosing a certain direction instead of others. Moreover, it presented us with the diversity of aims and needs that are placed on technology and must be balanced in its use. Simply put: the creation of music content can be a rewarding activity for people from diverse backgrounds and with diverse technological expertise. Therefore, encodings systems and related technologies need to provide different modes of engagement e.g., addressing different levels of interest or commitment. This refers back to the very core of user-centred design. As Don Norman pointed out already in 1986:¹⁰⁹ humans use technology to achieve their goals. In their use of technology, they face two gulfs: the

¹⁰⁹ D. A. Norman, 'Cognitive Engineering,' in *User Centered System Design: New Perspectives on Human-Computer Interaction*, eds. S.W. Draper and D.A. Norman (Erlbaum, 1986): 31-61.

Gulf of Execution when figuring out how something operates, and the Gulf of Evaluation when evaluating if an action has brought them closer to their goal. The design of technological systems is always concerned with narrowing this gulf, either by bringing people closer to technology or by bringing technology closer to people.

name, age	background	motivation	frustrations
David (c. 60)	choral conductor, has little interest in technology	find repertoire that makes singers happy, help others in same situation	existing editions always unsuitable
Dirk (73)	retired physics teacher, plays recorder and composes, unhappy marriage	publish transcriptions and compositions online, wants recognition for his efforts	web site doesn't get much traffic, maintenance is tedious
Elizabeth (late 60s)	retired geography teacher, single, amateur singer	learn more about the music she sings, find new music	wary of technology, really needs sense of community
Sebastian (mid 40s)	tech savvy, plays violin in amateur orchestra	save money by creating his own scores	expensive orchestral materials
Tanya (23)	music student, basic MuseScore user	publish transcriptions, write her own music, working with peers	considers herself a non-computer person, worried things go wrong

Table 4. Personas created during the workshop.

With regard to standardisation and data quality, this leads to a significant question in the role of technological systems for corpus creation: do we want to bring people closer to the technology by teaching them e.g., what 'good data' should look like? Or do we want to bring technology closer to the people who are using it? As the shift in our discussions based on the personas showed: aiming for the second option shifts the role of technology towards a system that helps negotiating people's aims and needs, for example by providing conversion procedures or multi-faceted access points. With such an approach there would be less need for them to modify their technical skills and preferences, while their intrinsic motivation to create codes and editions would remain unaffected.

7.3 Roles

We also discussed the collaborative process of music encoding in one of our sessions in connection with the ideas presented in Section 5.2. The aim was to create a generic workflow with tasks and roles that could be used as a template for

concrete encoding projects. Assuming a rather high level of organisation in the project, we initially we produced a quite elaborate diagram, which was subsequently reduced to the simple model of Figure 15 to fit a broader range of approaches.

Figure 15. High-level workflow of music encoding projects.

The model contains four main tasks, and multiple subtasks:

- instigation: setting the goals of the project; selecting compositions; creating a template for encodings; defining the project's success criteria;
- gathering: collection the materials to be used: metadata; digitised and physical sources; digital and physical editions; reusable encodings;
- editing: creating the encodings by means of OMR, manual transcription, encoding, and/or code conversion; integrating the raw transcription(s) into an edited encoding; correction and validation of the edited encoding;
- publishing: making the validated encodings available to the users.

This could be just a linear process, but more realistically it would involve feedback steps from publication to the three other tasks:

- to editing: integrate feedback from the users in the encodings;
- to gathering: enrich the encoding with newly-selected source materials, or reuse the encodings as base text for transcriptions of other versions of the same work, particularly close concordances;
- instigation: check the result against the goals and success criteria, potentially instigating a next cycle through the workflow.

In addition to the tasks, a number of roles is defined:

- instigator of the project: performs the tasks necessary to start off the project (see above);
- transcriber of sources: creates the raw encodings of the selected sources;
- computational specialist: in charge of OMR, conversion and other computational processes;
- editor: creates and edited encoding (or digital edition) from the raw encodings and the edition template; publishes edition after validation;

- validator: takes care of proof reading and quality checking;
- edition user: uses the materials for their own purposes and gives feedback to the project.

Leaving edition users aside, each role asks for a different set and/or level of expertise. For example, for transcribers a good working knowledge of music notation and a basic understanding of editing would suffice, while the editors need to possess both at a higher level. It depends on the ambition, scale, scope, embedding, funding and lifespan of a project if multiple (or even all) roles are relegated to a single person, or if each role is divided between multiple persons. In the case of transcribers and editors the latter seems obvious but large, structured projects are likely to have teams of instigators, computational specialists and validators.

8 Vision for the future of corpus building

Increasingly, musicians and music researchers engaged in early music do their work in the digital environment. Music is searched, transcribed and analysed by means of specialised software and services, editions are shared online, and research results are published in digital journals, conference proceedings, and books. Yet if we overview the digital landscape of early music, the dominant impression is one of relative fragmentation and scarcity of resources. This is especially true of what is arguably the fundamental precondition for most digital work in the field: the availability of music notation in digital, computer-processible form. Currently one cannot assume that for a given research problem in early music sufficient musical data containing the necessary features are available that can be analysed to solve it. Often there is such an investment in data creation and curation needed that a computational approach becomes infeasible. Therefore, a comprehensive approach to accelerate corpus creation in early music is urgently needed, aiming at a better coverage of the repertoire in a form that ideally is ready to be used, or, more realistically, needs a limited amount of work to make it ready for use.

We consider corpora and corpus creation to cover a broad range of products and activities, including the production of analytical encodings that contain only a few specific musical features, the encoding of the original notation of sources, and the creation of digital editions that meets scholarly and/or practical requirements. These activities have numerous commonalities in terms of how they are carried out on a day-to-day basis. They involve dealing with sources, notation forms, and editorial interventions, as well as working with similar technologies and encoding systems. Furthermore, they face the same problem of limited resources. There is so much work to be done with only limited financial means and human effort that sharing whatever can be shared between initiatives becomes imperative.

Corpus creation must thus be an inclusive endeavour. This applies not just to exchanging encodings, but to participation and technology as well. Music lovers and citizen scientists put a tremendous amount of effort into encoding music for their editions, often with impressive results. Professionals and amateurs use a variety of technologies for creating their encodings that fit their working methods and aims well. Any effort to coordinate their activities should start with a recognition of their motivations, musical skills, and technical choices. The challenge is to devise coordination mechanisms on top of these that respect their autonomy, yet help to spend resources wisely and stimulate participation.

Challenges do not end when the encoding is done. It must be possible to find encodings; they must possess attributes that document what they contain, how they were made and how they relate to other items in the digital ecosystem of early music. And they must remain accessible in the foreseeable future, on sustainable infrastructures. In the rest of this section, we will elaborate this vision in a number of

concrete aims. In the next section we will describe steps to realise some of these aims.

Coordination

- Create a group that acts as a glue between encoding and digital editing projects, collects experiences, advises ongoing projects and devises guidelines for the creation and sustainability of corpora. The current CORSICA team could form the core of this group.
- Create an inventory of encodings that are suitable for musicological work or as input for corpus creation (provisionally called RIEM – Répertoire International des Encodages Musicaux).
- Create a sustainable, decentralised platform with a small corpus of encoded scores, with the aim to grow little by little. This could also function as a repository for encodings created in short-term or small-scale projects lacking a publication platform.
- Create a metadata service that is reliable, in one place and being maintained, that provides unique IDs for various entities and can be incorporated into IMSLP, CPDL, and other already existing platforms.
- Create a unified user interface across the more important resources.

Participation

- Instead of building new communities, having a high risk of failure, identify the good (or promising) existing communities and build from there.
- Encoding of early music sources is democratised and is public domain.
- Mechanisms exist for acknowledging everyone's contribution in shared work, such that they closely align with motivations of the participants. They should feel comfortable in contributing to the corpus.
- Digital encoding/editing is part of the musicological curriculum: students learn to encode, to produce digital editions and to analyse encodings.
- Enable creation of encoding campaigns: identify an encoding challenge, create a workflow, divide the tasks over participants and integrate the work in a collective result.

Tools and support

- Develop an easy-to-use mobile-first editor for encoding to allow crowd-sourcing efforts.
- Design methods for a seamless and easy as possible conversion between encoding formats and notations.
- Tech workflows, such as for the encoding campaigns described above, are low-threshold, easy to use and freely available.
- Create a well-designed front end for distributing data and editions.
- Successful prototypes for music encoding software can be turned into stable and usable products.

The place of editions

- A new vision of music editing: a paradigm shift in our understanding of what a scholarly / critical monumental edition is, informed by CORSICA and DigME.¹¹⁰
- Implement this vision by co-designing dynamic digital editions with user communities to inform further development, and researching user interactions with various dynamic and static edition formats
- High-quality scores at the different editorial levels are widely available online

¹¹⁰ Digital Music Editions (DigME), <https://gtr.ukri.org/projects?ref=AH%2FV015095%2F1> (accessed 8 September 2025).

9 Implementation of the vision

While the above vision sets multiple long-term goals, the realisation of which may depend on a lot of factors outside of our control, we believe several concrete steps can already be taken within a reasonably short time frame.

User studies

- Run a survey of potential users and contributors.
- Continue the user research that was begun during the STSM by interviewing potential contributors and users, exploring their musical interests, work practices, motivation and engagement.
- Assemble a collection of user stories for different stakeholders.
- Do 'Wizard of Oz' experiments¹¹¹ with simulations and simple prototypes to study the interaction of users with encoding software.
- Write an article on user studies.

Communities and integration

- Get in contact with CPDL management to discuss:
 - needs of their contributors (knowledge, skills, resources, facsimiles);
 - to add attributes to their data that enable their use for musicological purposes;
 - ways of stimulating community engagement.
- Tackle the metadata problem. Step 1: make the serious website owners (DIAMM, RISM, MusicBrainz) aware of our problems and propose solutions that are relatively easy to implement.

Systems and process

- Analyse the workflows of successful corpus initiatives.
- Elaborate the conceptual map of roles, intermediate products, tasks and workflows (Section 7.3) into a generic model for corpus building.
- Create a platform for corpus creation with the primary aim of running experiments.
- Formulate a suggested transcription workflow to use with test contributors (e.g. undergraduate students), for example MuseScore → MEI friend.

Software and human-computer interaction

- Address conversion challenges such as:
 - CMME to MEI (which has been largely solved in the meantime);
 - Try conversion of Lilypond through OMR rather than code conversion.
- Perform further MuseScore integration experiments.

¹¹¹ In Wizard of Oz experiments some part of technology is simulated by human intervention, so that the effect of this technology on the user can be studied before it is implemented. See Benyon, *Designing User Experience*, 201-202.

- Focussed testing of metadata discovery and enrichment.
- User interface design:
 - Solve editorial markup from an editor's UI perspective;
 - HCI user experiment on validation approaches;
 - Create an attractive UI for for exploring, comparing, and visualising different versions of a composition.

References

- Baxendale, J., and F. Knights, eds. *The Fitzwilliam Virginal Book*. Lyrebird Music, 2020. 3 vols.
- Benyon, D. *Designing User Experience*. Pearson UK, 2019.
- Biber, D. 'Representativeness in Corpus Design.' *Literary and linguistic computing* 8, no. 4 (1993): 243–257. <https://doi.org/10.1093/lc/8.4.243>.
- Call, J., C. Hamm, and H. Kellman. *Census-Catalogue of Manuscript Sources of Polyphonic Music, 1400–1550*. American Institute of Musicology, Hänssler-Verlag, 1979–1988. 5 vols.
- Calvo-Zaragoza, J., J. Hajič Jr., and A. Pacha. 'Understanding Optical Music Recognition.' *ACM Computing Surveys* 53, no. 4 (2020): article 77. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3397499>.
- Coney, D. 'The David Melville Bassus Partbook and Scottish Music Culture at the Turn of the 17th Century.' Paper presented at the International Medieval and Renaissance Music Conference, Durham, U.K, July 2025.
- Crawford, T. 'A Digital Corpus for Exploring the Lute Music of John Dowland (1563–1626).' *Journal of New Music Research* 53, no. 3–4 (2025): 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09298215.2025.2486139>.
- Crawford, T., D. Lewis, and A. Porter. 'Exploring Early Vocal Music and Its Lute Arrangements: Using F-TEMPO as a Musicological Tool.' In *DLfM '23: Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Digital Libraries for Musicology*. Edited by M.E. Thomae. Association for Computing Machinery, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3625135.3625142>.
- Cumming, J., C. McKay, J. Stuchbery, and I. Fujinaga. 'Methodologies for Creating Symbolic Corpora of Western Music Before 1600.' In *Proceedings of the 19th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference*. Edited by E. Gómez, X. Hu, E. Humphrey, and E. Benetos. 2018. <https://archives.ismir.net/ismir2018/paper/000026.pdf>.
- Cuthbert, M. S. 'Tipping the Iceberg: Missing Italian Polyphony from the Age of Schism.' *Musica Disciplina* 54 (2009): 39–74. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25750547>.
- De Luca, E., and H. Utidjian. 'Challenging the MEI Neumes Module: Encoding Armenian Neumes.' In *Music Encoding Conference 2022 Proceedings*. Edited by A. Ang, J. Bain, and D. M. Weigl. 2023. <https://doi.org/10.17613/gnnp-z327>.
- Fiala, D., L. Pugin, M. van Berchum, M. Thomae, and K. Roger. 'A New XML Conversion Process for Mensural Music Encoding: CMME_to_MEI (via Verovio).' Paper presented at the Music Encoding Conference, London, 4 June 2025. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2507.15991>.
- Flanders, J., and F. Jannidis, eds. *The Shape of Data in Digital Humanities: Modeling Texts and Text-Based Resources*. Routledge, 2019.
- Fresquet, X. 'Artificial Neural Networks and Medieval Music.' *Early Music* 52, no. 3 (2024): 298–317. <https://doi.org/10.1093/em/caae039>.
- Fujinaga, I., and G. Vigiensoni. 'Optical Music Recognition Workflow for Medieval Music Manuscripts.' In *Proceedings of the 5th Workshop on Reading Music Systems*. Edited by J. Calvo-Zaragoza, A. Pacha, and E. Shatri. 2023. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2311.04091>.
- Goebel, W., and D.M. Weigl. 'mei-friend: An Interactive Web-Based Editor for Digital Music Encodings.' *Journal of Open Source Software* 9, no. 98 (2024): 6002. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.06002>.

- Gotham, M., P. Jonas, B. Bower, W. Bosworth, D. Rootham, and L. VanHandel. 'Scores of Scores: An Openscore Project to Encode and Share Sheet Music.' In *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Digital Libraries for Musicology*. Edited by K. Page. Association for Computing Machinery, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3273024.3273026>.
- Graczyk, S., Z. Piniarska, M. Kałamoniak, T. Łukaszewski, and E. Łukasik. 'An Online Tool for Semi-Automatically Annotating Music Scores for Optical Music Recognition.' In *Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Digital Libraries for Musicology*. Edited by D.M. Weigl. Association for Computing Machinery, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3660570.3660571>.
- Hajič, jr., J., and F.C. Moss. 'Knowing When to Stop: Insights from Ecology for Building Catalogues, Collections, and Corpora. In *DLfM '25: Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Digital Libraries for Musicology*. Edited by E. De Luca. Association for Computing Machinery, 2024): <https://doi.org/10.1145/3748336.3748347>.
- Hajič jr., J., P. Žabička, J. Rychtář, et al. 'The OmniOMR Project.' In *Proceedings of the 5th Workshop on Reading Music Systems*. Edited by J. Calvo-Zaragoza, A. Pacha, and E. Shatri. 2023. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2311.04091>.
- Hankinson, A., P. Roland, and I. Fujinaga. 'The Music Encoding Initiative as a Document-Encoding Framework.' In *Proceedings of the 12th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference*. Edited by A. Klapuri and C. Leider. 2011. <https://archives.ismir.net/ismir2011/paper/000011.pdf>.
- Hankinson A., J. A. Burgoyne, G. Vigiensoni, et al. 'Digital Document Image Retrieval Using Optical Music Recognition.' In *Proceedings of the 13th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference*. Edited by F. Gouyon, P. Herrera, L.G. Martins, and M. Müller. 2012. https://ismir2012.ismir.net/event/papers/577_ISMIR_2012.pdf.
- He, R., and Yao, J. (2024). 'End-to-End Optical Music Recognition with Attention Mechanism and Memory Units Optimization.' In *Pattern Recognition and Computer Vision. PRCV 2023*. Edited by Q. Liu, H. Wang, Z. Ma, et al. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, 14426. Springer, 2024. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-8432-9_32.
- Hemerly, J. 'Making Metadata: The Case of MusicBrainz.' Master's thesis, University of California, Berkeley, 2009. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1982823.
- lñesta, J.M., D. Rizo, and J. Calvo-Zaragoza. 'MuRET as a Software for the Transcription of Historical Archives.' In *Proceedings of the 2nd Workshop on Reading Music Systems*. Edited by J. Calvo-Zaragoza and A. Pacha. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2212.00380>.
- Javanmardi S., Y. Ganjisaffar, C. Lopes, and P. Baldi. 'User Contribution and Trust in Wikipedia.' In *Proceedings of the 5th International ICST Conference on Collaborative Computing: Networking, Applications, Worksharing*. Edited by J. Joshi and T. Zhang. 2009. <https://doi.org/10.4108/icst.collaboratecom2009.8376>.
- Kestemont, M., F. Karsdorp, E. de Bruijn, et al. 'Forgotten Books: The Application of Unseen Species Models to the Survival of Culture.' *Science* 375, issue 6582. 2022. <https://www.doi.org/10.1126/science.abl7655>.
- Leuchtman, H. *Orlando di Lasso. Seine Werke in zeitgenössischen Drucken 1555-1687*. Bärenreiter, 2001. 3 vols.

- Lewis, D., T. Crawford, and D. Müllensiefen. 'Instrumental Idiom in the 16th Century: Embellishment Patterns in Arrangements of Vocal Music.' In *Proceedings of the 12th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference*. Edited by M.I. Mandel, J. Devaney, D. Turnbull, and G. Tzanetakis. 2016. <https://archives.ismir.net/ismir2016/paper/000165.pdf>.
- Luthra, M., and M. Eskevich. 'Data-Envelopes for Cultural Heritage: Going beyond Datasheets.' In *Proceedings of the Workshop on Legal and Ethical Issues in Human Language Technologies @ LREC-COLING 2024*. Edited by I. Siegert and K. Choukri. ELRA and ICCL, 2024. <https://aclanthology.org/2024.legal-1.9>.
- Mayer, J., M. Straka, M., J. Hajič jr., and P. Pecina, P. (2024). 'Practical End-to-End Optical Music Recognition for Pianoform Music.' In *Document Analysis and Recognition - ICDAR 2024*. Edited by E.H. Barney Smith, M. Liwicki, and L. Peng. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, 14809. Springer, 2024. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-70552-6_4.
- A. Mendel, A. 'Some Preliminary Attempts at Computer-Assisted Style Analysis in Music.' *Computers and the Humanities* 4, no. 2 (1969): 41-52. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/30199321>.
- Meyer, C.F. *English Corpus Linguistics: An Introduction*. 2nd ed. Cambridge University Press, 2023.
- Norman, Donald A. 'Cognitive Engineering'. In *User Centered System Design: New Perspectives on Human-Computer Interaction*. Edited by S.W. Draper and D.A. Norman. Erlbaum, 1986.
- Penarrubia, C., J.J. Valero-Mas, and J. Calvo-Zaragoza. 'Contrastive Self-Supervised Learning for Optical Music Recognition.' In *Document Analysis Systems. DAS 2024*. Edited by G. Sfikas and G. Retsinas. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, 14994. Springer, 2024. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-70442-0_19.
- Peter Philips and Richard Dering: Consort Music*. Edited by D.J. Smith. Musica Britannica 101. Stainer & Bell, 2016.
- Peter Philips: Complete Keyboard Music*. Edited by D.J. Smith. Musica Britannica 75. Stainer & Bell, 1999.
- Plaksin, A.V.K. 'Modelle zur computergestützten Analyse von Überlieferungen der Mensuralmusik: Empirische Textforschung im Kontext phylogenetischer Verfahren.' PhD diss., Technische Universität Darmstadt, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.26083/tuprints-00017211>.
- Puentes-Blanco, A., M. Kokole, P. Vendrix, et al. 'The Monumental Edition in the Digital Age: Creating a Sustainable Future.' *Journal of New Music Research* 53, no. 3-4 (2024): 312-324. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09298215.2024.2373998>.
- Pugin, L. 'Interaction with Music Encoding.' In *"Ei, dem alten Herrn zoll' ich Achtung gern"* *Festschrift für Joachim Veit zum 60. Geburtstag*. Edited by K. Richts and P. Stadler. Allitera Verlag, 2016. <https://musiconn.qucosa.de/api/qucosa%3A23351/attachment/ATT-0/>.
- Pugin L., and T. Crawford. 'Evaluating OMR on the Early Music Online Collection.' In *Proceedings of the 14th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference*. Edited by A. de Souza Britto jr., F. Gouyon, and S. Dixon. 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3625135.3625142>.
- Richt, K. 'Die FRBR Customization im Datenformat der Music Encoding Initiative (MEI).' Master's thesis, Cologne University of Applied Sciences, 2013. <https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:hbz:79pbc-2013103042>.

- Ríos-Vila, A., J. Calvo-Zaragoza, and T. Paquet. 'Sheet Music Transformer: End-To-End Optical Music Recognition beyond Monophonic Transcription.' In *Document Analysis and Recognition - ICDAR 2024*. Edited by E.H. Barney Smith, M. Liwicki, and L. Peng. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, 14809. Springer, 2024. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-70552-6_2.
- Robison, T.D. 'IML-MIR: A Data-Processing System for the Analysis of Music.' In *Elektronische Datenverarbeitung in der Musikwissenschaft*. Edited by H. Heckmann. Gustav Bosse Verlag, 1967.
- Rodríguez-García, E., and C. McKay. 'Composer Attribution of Renaissance Motets: A Case Study Using Statistical Features and Machine Learning.' In *The Anatomy of Iberian Polyphony around 1500*. Edited by E. Rodríguez-García and J. P. d'Alvarenga. Reichenberger, 2021.
- Rodríguez-García, E., and C. McKay. 'Composer Attribution of Renaissance Motets (Iberian Polyphony around 1500): MIDIs and Extracted Features.' Data set. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4027957>.
- Roselló, A., E. Fuentes-Martínez, M. Alfaro-Contreras, D. Rizo, and J. Calvo-Zaragoza. 'Source-Free Domain Adaptation for Optical Music Recognition.' In *Document Analysis and Recognition - ICDAR 2024*. Edited by E.H. Barney Smith, M. Liwicki, and L. Peng. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, 14809. Springer, 2024. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-70552-6_2.
- Selfridge-Field, E., ed. *Beyond MIDI: The Handbook of Musical Codes*. The MIT Press, 1998.
- Smith, D.J. 'The Instrumental Music of Peter Philips.' PhD diss., University of Oxford, 1994. <https://ora.ox.ac.uk/objects/uuid:d1af3140-2553-4f58-8437-a1eee66d7f13/files/m06f60f301b6cca42daeeca7b3508cd0a>.
- Smith, D.J., and A. Woolley. 'Editing Purcell's Keyboard Music: Some Reflections on Collected Editions, Past and Future.' *Journal of New Music Research* 53, no. 3-4 (2024): 277-296. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09298215.2025.2472612>.
- Stachowiak, H. *Allgemeine Modelltheorie*. Springer, 1973.
- Tuggener, L., R. Emberger, A. Ghosh, et al. 'Real World Music Object Recognition.' *Transactions of the International Society for Music Information Retrieval* 7, no. 1 (2024): 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.5334/tismir.157>.
- Tuppen, S., S. Rose, and L. Drosopoulou. 'Library Catalogue Records as a Research Resource: Introducing "a Big Data History of Music".' *Fontes Artis Musicae* 63 (2016): 67-88. <https://doi.org/10.1353/fam.2016.0011>.
- Umbreit, J., and S. Schumann. 'OMR on Early Music Sources at the Bavarian State Library with MuRET - Prototyping, Automating, Scaling.' In *Proceedings of the 6th Workshop on Reading Music Systems*. Edited by J. Calvo-Zaragoza, A. Pacha, and E. Shatri. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2411.15741>.
- Wiering, F. 'Digital Critical Editions of Music: A Multidimensional Model.' In *Modern Methods for Musicology: Prospects, Proposals, and Realities*. Edited by T. Crawford and L. Gibson. Ashgate, 2009.
- Wiering F., and C. Inskip. 'The Impact of the Pandemic on Musicologists' Use of Technology.' *Digital Humanities Quarterly* 19, no. 2 (2025). <https://dhq.digitalhumanities.org/vol/19/2/000786/000786.html>.
- Wikimedia Foundation. 'Corpus Linguistics.' https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Corpus_linguistics.

Appendices

Appendix 1: CORSICA proposal

Name of host	Frans Wiering
Host Institution	Utrecht University, Department of Information and Computing Sciences, Music Information Computing group
Role of host and host institution	Host will guide the STSM project, plan activities, organise online preparation meetings, the workshop, and follow-up meeting(s) if these are needed. The host institution will provide working space for the workshop. In addition to the host, 1-2 researchers from the host institution will participate in the workshop.
Time period	Workshop will take place either in the week of 13-17 May 2024. Online activities will take place in the weeks before and immediately after the workshop.
Number of guests	c. 7 guests, from multiple countries
Working group	WG2, Sources; WG3, Publications
Objective of STSM project	<p>Analysis of large textual corpora has revealed new insights in many historical fields. Projects such as ECOLM and the Stanford Josquin Project show that a corpus-based approach also works in the music domain. There are important differences though. Whereas textual corpora have been created at a large scale and are relatively homogeneous, musical corpora are comparatively small and show a considerable variety in encoding practices. For pre-1700 polyphonic music, the situation is especially complicated: few corpora contain more than several hundreds of items; different types of music notation such as mensural notation and tablature pose specific encoding problems; and transcription to modern notation can be supported in a number of ways.</p> <p>Some of the consequences of this state of affairs are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Available corpora are not a representative selection of the known repertoire; • Off-the-beaten-track research requires an excessive

	<p>amount of encoding effort;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality and interoperability issues increase when using multiple corpora; • PhD students and early-career researchers do not have sufficient resources to embark on a career as digital musicologists. <p>On the other hand, there are some important positive developments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The emergence of MEI (Music Encoding Initiative) as a versatile 'musicological' encoding system with a growing community of users; • Improvements in Optical Music Recognition for early music; • The general practice of musicologists to use music notation software to create their transcriptions; • A growing practice of online sharing of editions created by both professional and amateur musicians. <p>In the past, the solution for the lack of encodings has often been sought in standardisation and training. Such endeavours have often met with limited success for at least four interconnected reasons: limited tool support; required time investment for learning; loss of already created work; and most importantly loss of autonomy. The logical alternative is therefore to consider autonomy and variety of practices as starting points for a new paradigm of corpus creation. Some elements of this are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contribute encodings with minimal effort; • Metadata for effective documentation of encoding practices; • Interoperability rather than standardisation; • A set of intuitive tools for common tasks; • Practical guidelines for sharing and exchanging encodings; • Involving music professionals and lay experts in the encoding process; • Making participation rewarding and fun. <p>Realising these (and other necessary) ambitions will take a multi-year effort, which could take its first steps towards</p>
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	<p>maturity in the environment of the EarlyMuse COST action. We propose this STSM project named 'Creation Of eaRly muSic CorporA' (CORSICA) as the first of these steps. A small group of experts will come together to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survey the current state of the art in corpus creation of early music; • Identify bottlenecks and opportunities; • Create a vision document for accelerating corpus creation; • Create an implementation plan with practical recommendations.
<p>Relation to WG and Action goals</p>	<p>The project is related to the following goals and objectives:</p> <p>MoU, Secondary objective 3: <i>preservation of musical heritage and accessibility of resources</i>. As a logical next step after digitisation, corpus creation increases deep access to sources as well as a way of preserving the content, not just the appearance, of a source.</p> <p>MoU, Secondary objective 3: <i>creating a multidisciplinary research network</i>. By creating larger corpora in a more systematic fashion, it becomes easier use these data in an interdisciplinary context, where researchers may not have the specialist knowledge that is currently necessary to employ corpora fruitfully. Larger corpora also allow a wider range of research problems to be addressed, so that a network of researchers with multiple interest can emerge around them. For early-career researchers this is particularly beneficial as they are no longer obliged to create their own digital research environment from scratch.</p> <p>GAPG 3 (WG2): <i>describe ways of identifying and describing endangered musical sources (including in Ukraine)</i>. There may be tenuous relation to this goal, in that encoding can be seen as protection of the content. For example, community initiatives that aim to digitise their own musical heritage could be supported by guidelines that make this as straightforward as possible and at the same time compatible with scholarly approaches.</p> <p>GAPG 4 (WG3): <i>Imagining innovative publication models</i>. Several connections seem relevant:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The increasing importance of reproducibility of research. Publishing a corpus, or referring to an existing corpus as underlying data makes research easier to reproduce; • Corpora could be seen as publications: one's contributions to a corpus become part of one's academic portfolio; • Encodings relate to digital editions in two ways: they can be used as input to an editorial process in which they are further refined, for example by collating multiple sources of the same work; or the edited work can be stored as an analysable encoding. <p>GAPG 6 (WG2): <i>establish an information exchange protocol with RISM</i>. CORSICA has a deep connection to RISM. RISM may provide essential metadata that improve the quality, usability and accessibility of the compositions in a corpus. It may also play an essential role in the selection of items to be encoded and in addressing questions of representativeness. Conversely, the act of encoding of encoding will produce new metadata that need to be compliant with RISM and that may in some cases be used to correct or enhance the RISM data itself. In fact, corpus creation is an ideal case study for GAPG 6 itself.</p>
<p>Expected outcomes / deliverables</p>	<p>The following outcomes are expected:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A report describing the current state of the art in corpus creation of early music • A vision on how to accelerate corpus corpus creation • A plan for implementing this vision
<p>Short summary</p>	<p>CORSICA (Creation Of eaRly muSic CorporA) will address the shortage of large-scale corpora of encoded early music. Existing corpora are generally small (usually less than 1000 items) and display a variety of encoding practices. This makes large-scale computational analysis of the music currently unfeasible. Experts in the field will come together in a 1-week workshop in Utrecht (Netherlands) to survey the current state of early music encoding; to identify bottlenecks and opportunities (in terms of technologies as well as communities); to create a vision for the future and to define practical steps towards accelerating corpus creation in early music.</p>

Appendix 2: Early music corpora

CORPUS DESCRIPTIONS

corpus name	musical content	data	creation method	url
Accessible Lute Music	Lute music from Renaissance and Baroque	accessible corpus	citizen science	https://wp.lutemusic.org/
Archive of Iberian Polyphony	Iberian polyphony from the Renaissance	digital editions, non-public encodings	academic research	https://iberianpolyphony.fcsh.unl.pt/
Choral Public Domain Library (CPDL)	Choral music of any age	encodings available for many works	citizen science	https://www.cpdl.org/wiki/
Citations: The Renaissance Imitation Mass (CRIM)	16th c. imitation masses and their models	accessible corpus	academic research	https://crimproject.org/
Classical Archives	Western composers, 14-20th century	accessible corpus	citizen science	https://www.classicalarchives.com/midi.html
Computerized Mensural Music Editing (CMME)	15-16th c. polyphony, with works by Josquin, Berchem and others	accessible corpus	academic research	http://www.cmme.org/ ; https://github.com/tdumitrescu/cmme-music
Electronic Corpus of Lute Music (ECOLM)	Lute music from Renaissance and Baroque	accessible corpus, password protected	academic research	https://ecolm.org
Electronic Linked Annotated Unified Tablature Edition (E-LAUTE)	Lute music from the German-speaking areas, mainly in German lute tablature	accessible corpus	academic research	https://e-laute.info/
Electronic Medieval Music Score Archive Project (EMMSAP)	14th century music	accessible corpus	academic research	https://github.com/cuthbertLab/emmsap
ELVIS database	Contains multiple subcollections, some also existing as separate corpora. Includes compositions printed in Glarean's Dodekachordon, works by Palestrina, Victoria and others	accessible corpus	academic research	https://github.com/ELVIS-Project
Furnace and Fugue	Digital edition of Atalanta fugiens (1618), music composed by Michael Meier	digital editions, non-public encodings	academic research	https://furnaceandfugue.org/
Gaffurius Codices Online (MCE)	Polyphony from c. 1500, with works by Compere, Weerbeke, Gaffurius and others	digital editions, non-public encodings	academic research	https://www.gaffurius-codices.ch/s/portal/page/editions

corpus name	musical content	data	creation method	url
Gaspar Online Edition	Collected works of Gaspar van Weerbeke	accessible corpus	academic research	http://www.gaspar-van-weerbeke.sbg.ac.at/gaspar-online-edition
Gesualdo online	Complete works of Gesualdo	accessible corpus	academic research	https://ricercar.gesualdo-online.cesr.univ-tours.fr/
Goldberg Corpus	15th and early 16th century music	non-public encodings	citizen science	https://www.goldbergstiftung.org/en/
Johannes Tinctoris Complete Practical Works	Practical works of Johannes Tinctoris, 3 pieces by Dufay, and 2 by Busnois	accessible corpus	academic research	https://earlymusictheory.org/Tinctoris/Music/
John Robinson/Lute Society editions	Lute music from Renaissance and Baroque	accessible corpus	citizen science	https://github.com/TimCrawford/jhr_repo
Josquin La Rue Secure Duo Dataset	Duos from masses by Josquin and La Rue	accessible corpus	academic research	https://github.com/ELVIS-Project/mass-duos-corpus-josquin-larue/tree/Methodologies-for-Creating-Symbolic-Music-Corpora
Josquin Research project (JRP)	Works by Josquin and contemporaries	accessible corpus	academic research	https://josquin.stanford.edu/
KernScores	Western composers, 14-20th century, with works by Frescobaldi, Monteverdi, Corelli and others	accessible corpus	mix	http://kern.ccarh.org/
Kunst der Fuge	Western composers, 14-20th century	accessible corpus	citizen science	https://kunstderfuge.com/midi.htm
Lassus Tricinium Project	Tricinia by Orlande and Rudolph de Lassus	accessible corpus	academic research	https://lassus.mh-freiburg.de/ ; https://github.com/WolfgangDrescher/lassus-geistliche-psalmen
Lost Voices	16th c. French chansons	accessible corpus	academic research	http://digitalduchemin.org/
Marenzio Online Digital Edition (MODE)	Works by Marenzio	non-public encodings	academic research	http://www.marenzio.org/index.xhtml
Measuring polyphony	14th century motets	accessible corpus	academic research	https://measuringpolyphony.org/ ; https://github.com/MeasuringPolyphony/mp-music-files
Miami Publication Server (University of Münster)	Digital editions of early 17th c. sacred music by Crüger and Textorius	accessible corpus	academic research	https://miami.uni-muenster.de/
Music21 corpus	Western composers, 14-20th century	accessible corpus	mix	https://www.music21.org/music21/docs/about/referenceCorpus.html
Neuma	Contains multiple subcollections, with works by Josquin, Ockeghem, Dufay, Frescobaldi and others	accessible corpus	academic research	http://neuma.huma-num.fr/
Polish Digital Scores	Polish music, 16th-20th century	accessible corpus	academic research	https://polishscores.org/

corpus name	musical content	data	creation method	url
Single Interface for Music Score Searching and Analysis (SIMMSA)	Heterogeneous corpus, aggregated from various other corpora	accessible corpus	academic research	https://simssa.ca/activities/corpora-and-datasets/
Symbolically Encoded Il Lauro Secco (SEILS)	Madrigals by various composers published in Il Lauro Secco (1582)	accessible corpus	academic research	https://github.com/SEILSdataset
Tasso in Music	Musical settings of Tasso's poems, with works by Monteverdi, Marenzio, Wert, Cifra, others	accessible corpus	academic research	https://www.tassomusic.org/
The 1520s Project	1520s polyphony, with works by Willaert, Senfl, Verdelot and others	accessible corpus	academic research	https://1520s-project.org/about/
Tomás Luis de Victoria	Spanish music from Morales onward, including works by Guerrero, Victoria, Ceballos, Vasquez	accessible corpus	citizen science	https://www.uma.es/victoria/index.html
Verovio Humdrum Viewer	Various encodings, mostly from other projects such as 1, 8, 9, 25	accessible corpus	academic research	https://verovio.humdrum.org

CORPUS SIZES AND ENCODINGS

Supported formats are indicated by 'x'; storage formats used to derive other formats from are indicated by 'o'.

corpus name	items before 1700	ASCII tablature	CMME	Humdrum	Lilypond	MEI	MIDI	MP3	MuseData	MusicXML/Finale	PDF	Sibelius	Other
Accessible Lute Music	c. 17000	o					x				x		
Archive of Iberian Polyphony	130						x			o	x	o	
Choral Public Domain Library (CPDL)	c. 30000				x		x			x	x		x
Citations: The Renaissance Imitation Mass (CRIM)	c. 300					o					x		
Classical Archives	several 100s						o						
Computerized Mensural Music Editing (CMME)	c. 260		o										
Electronic Corpus of Lute Music (ECOLM)	1619	o											
Electronic Linked Annotated Unified Tablature Edition (E-LAUTE)	60, growing					o							
Electronic Medieval Music Score Archive Project (EMMSAP)	3600									x			
ELVIS database	c. 1000						x			x	x		x
Furnace and Fugue	50					o					x	o	
Gaffurius Codices Online (MCE)	c. 55					o							
Gaspar Online Edition	c. 100			x		x				o			
Gesualdo online	222					o					x		
Goldberg Corpus	3600		o			x							
Johannes Tinctoris Complete Practical Works	c. 50					x							o
John Robinson/Lute Society editions	c. 8000	o				x					x		
Josquin La Rue Secure Duo Dataset	77						x			x	x	o	
Josquin Research project (JRP)	902			o		x	x	x	x	x	x		x
KernScores	c. 350			o			x						
Kunst der Fuge	several 100s						o						
Lassus Tricinium Project	50			o		x							
Lost Voices	c. 350					x					x	o	
Marenzio Online Digital Edition (MODE)	32					o					x		
Measuring polyphony	61					o				x	x	x	

corpus name	items before 1700	ASCII tablature	CMMME	Humdrum	Lilypond	MEI	MIDI	MP3	MuseData	MusicXML/Finale	PDF	Sibelius	Other
Miami Publication Server (University of Münster)	c. 230						x				o		
Music21 corpus	several 100s			x						x			x
Neuma	c. 600				x	x				x			
Polish Digital Scores	1740			o		x	x		x	x			x
Single Interface for Music Score Searching and Analysis (SIMMSA)	???			x		x	x			x	x		x
Symbolically Encoded Il Lauro Secco (SEILS)	30			x	o		x			x	x		
Tasso in Music	778			o		x	x	x	x	x	x		x
The 1520s Project	491			x		x	x			x	x	o	
Tomás Luis de Victoria	c. 1000				o		x				x		
Verovio Humdrum Viewer	c. 1500			o		x				x			